

On the Analysis of Misspecified Variational Inequalities with Nonlinear Constraints

Novel Kumar Dey

Department of Applied Mathematics, The University of Arizona, ndey@arizona.edu

Mohammad Mahdi Ahmadi

Department of Systems and Industrial Engineering, The University of Arizona, ahmadi@arizona.edu

Erfan Yazdandoost Hamedani

Department of Systems and Industrial Engineering, The University of Arizona, erfany@arizona.edu

Afroz Jalilzadeh

Department of Systems and Industrial Engineering, The University of Arizona, afroz@arizona.edu

Abstract. In this paper, we study a class of misspecified variational inequalities (VIs) where both the monotone operator and nonlinear convex constraints depend on an unknown parameter learned via a secondary VI. Existing data-driven VI methods typically follow a decoupled learn-then-optimize scheme, causing the approximation error from the learning to propagate the main decision-making problem and hinder convergence. We instead consider a simultaneous approach that jointly solves the main and secondary VIs. To efficiently handle nonlinear constraints with parameter misspecification, we propose a single-loop inexact Augmented Lagrangian method that simultaneously updates the primal decision variables, dual multipliers, and the misspecified parameter. The method combines a forward-reflected-backward step with an Augmented Lagrangian penalty, and explicitly handles misspecification on both the operator and constraint functions. Moreover, we introduce a relaxed performance metric based on the Minty VI gap combined with an aggregated infeasibility metric. By proving boundedness of the dual iterates, we establish $O(1/K)$ ergodic convergence rates for these metrics. Numerical experiments are provided to showcase the superior performance of our algorithm compared to state-of-the-art methods.

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1. Introduction

Variational inequality (VI) problems have received significant attention in recent years owing to their general formulation that unifies a wide spectrum of well-known problems, including constrained and unconstrained optimization, saddle point (SP) problems, and Nash equilibrium problems (Facchinei and Pang 2003). These formulations naturally arise in diverse domains such as machine learning, economics, and game theory. Classical formulations assume complete knowledge of the problem parameters and feasible sets, enabling deterministic analysis of equilibria and their stability properties. However, in many practical applications, ranging from networked systems and energy markets to learning-based decision models, the underlying parameters governing the VI are not known precisely and must instead be inferred from data or auxiliary learning processes. This leads to *misspecified variational inequalities*, where the true problem data depend on an unknown parameter vector that is estimated imperfectly. Such misspecification introduces an inherent coupling between the estimation and optimization components, giving rise to new analytical and computational challenges.

In contrast to stochastic or robust optimization approaches (Jiang and Xu 2008, Nemirovski et al. 2009, Juditsky et al. 2011, Koshal et al. 2012) that assume access to distributional information or uncertainty sets, misspecified VIs capture settings in which the unknown parameters evolve through

a separate, possibly *data-driven*, mechanism. This perspective bridges classical equilibrium modeling with modern learning paradigms, allowing for adaptive decision-making under uncertainty without explicit probabilistic assumptions. While recent advances have established foundational results for misspecified VIs Ahmadi and Shanbhag (2020), Jiang and Shanbhag (2016) in unconstrained or affine settings, the incorporation of nonlinear constraints remains largely unexplored.

In this paper, we address a class of *misspecified constrained variational inequality* in which both the operator and the constraint functions depend on an unknown parameter vector θ^* . Specifically, we seek (x^*, θ^*) such that

$$F(x^*, \theta^*)^\top (y - x^*) \geq 0, \quad \forall y \in \mathcal{X}(\theta^*), \quad (\text{Misspecified VI})$$

where $F : \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^m \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ is a continuous mapping, and $\mathcal{X} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n$ is the feasible set defined by

$$\mathcal{X}(\theta^*) \triangleq \{x \in X \mid f_j(x, \theta^*) \leq 0, \quad \forall j = 1, \dots, J\}, \quad \text{and} \quad X \triangleq \prod_{i=1}^N X_i. \quad (1)$$

Each $X_i \subseteq \mathbb{R}^{n_i}$ is a nonempty, closed, and convex set, and $f_j(\cdot, \theta^*)$ is convex in x . The parameter $\theta^* \in \Theta \subseteq \mathbb{R}^m$ is not known a priori; instead, it is determined as the solution of a secondary variational inequality

$$H(\theta^*)^\top (\vartheta - \theta^*) \geq 0, \quad \forall \vartheta \in \Theta, \quad (2)$$

where $H : \mathbb{R}^m \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m$ is a continuous and strongly monotone mapping, and $\Theta \subseteq \mathbb{R}^m$ is a nonempty, closed, and convex set. This coupled VI-within-VI framework simulates, for instance, network or market equilibria where the feasible set and operator are contingent upon demand or cost parameters derived from historical data, or policy-constrained Cournot competition with unobserved prices collected from empirical observations. Our focus is on algorithmic frameworks that *simultaneously* update the primal variable x , the dual multipliers associated with the nonlinear constraints, and the parameter estimate θ . To address the challenges posed by nonlinear constraints in the misspecified VI framework, we employ an augmented Lagrangian approach (Alizadeh et al. 2024). This method embeds the nonlinear constraints into the objective through a Lagrange multiplier term combined with a quadratic penalty, thereby enforcing feasibility progressively.

1.1. Literature Review

A wide body of work has examined VI problems, including foundational results for deterministic VIs (Tseng 2000, Nemirovski 2004, Solodov and Tseng 1996, Solodov and Svaiter 2000) and their stochastic counterparts (Juditsky et al. 2011, Nemirovski et al. 2009, Lan and Ouyang 2021). In this section, we review prevailing methodologies for optimization problems involving unknown or misspecified parameters, studied across frameworks such as constrained minimization, saddle point formulations, and VI models.

Constraint-based Minimization. In this line of research, numerous works focus on objective function minimization under both deterministic (Ahmadi et al. 2016, Ahmadi and Shanbhag 2014,

Aybat et al. 2021) and stochastic frameworks (Jiang and Shanbhag 2016, Yang and Lei 2025, Yang et al. 2025a). In the deterministic setting, Ahmadi and Shanbhag (2014) study a misspecified convex optimization problem of the form $\min_{x \in X} f(x; \theta^*)$ subject to $\theta^* \in \arg \min_{\theta \in \Theta} g(\theta)$. When both the optimization and learning objectives are strongly convex, the coupled update scheme achieves a linear convergence rate. In contrast, when $f(\cdot; \theta^*)$ is merely convex while g remains strongly convex and a weak-sharpness condition is satisfied, the standard $O(1/K)$ rate is retained. Aybat et al. (2021) consider a convex optimization problem with a constraint set that depends on an unknown parameter and introduce an inexact parametric augmented Lagrangian method (IPALM) to handle this misspecification. The scheme employs an accelerated proximal-gradient step for updating the optimization decision variable and an outer update of the multipliers. They derive iteration-complexity bounds showing that, under constant and increasing penalty sequences, IPALM requires at most $O(K^{-1/4})$ and $O(\log K/K)$, respectively.

Saddle Point (SP) and Variational Inequality (VI) Problems. Recent research has extended the study of misspecification beyond classical optimization to SP and VI problems. In (Ahmadi and Shanbhag 2020), a class of misspecified monotone VI problems is studied, where misspecifications may arise in the objective. To tackle these issues, the authors develop extragradient and regularized first-order algorithms tailored for misspecified monotone VI problems coupled with strongly convex learning subproblems, thereby guaranteeing stable convergence. Complementary to this, (Jiang and Shanbhag 2016) analyze stochastic variational inequality (SVI) problems in the context of misspecification, covering both stochastic convex optimization and a range of stochastic equilibrium models. Their analysis critically relies on the strong convexity of the learning problem, which guarantees convergence of both the optimization and learning iterates. They further establish almost-sure convergence in strongly monotone settings, achieving the optimal rate of $O(1/K)$, and in merely monotone settings by employing iterative Tikhonov regularization, which yields a rate of $O(\sqrt{\log K}/\sqrt{K})$ under weak sharpness. Ahmadi and Shanbhag (2020) extend their earlier work Ahmadi and Shanbhag (2014) to misspecified monotone variational inequality problems and show that a constant-step-length misspecified extragradient scheme achieves asymptotic convergence of the iterates. More recently, Ahmadi and Hamedani (2025) examine a class of misspecified convex-concave SP problems where the misspecified parameter can be obtained through a secondary SP problem with a strongly convex-concave objective function. They introduce a Learning-aware Accelerated Primal-Dual method that integrates the parameter updates directly into the dual momentum step and utilizes an adaptive backtracking scheme to select step sizes adaptively. Their approach attains a convergence rate of $O(\log K/K)$ without relying on compactness of the feasible sets. In addition, they extend their method to settings where the secondary SP problem may not have a unique solution, proving that a modified version of the algorithm tailored to this structure achieves a rate of $O(1/\sqrt{K})$ in terms of both gap function and learning suboptimality.

1.2. Research Gap and Our Contribution

Previous work on misspecified VIs has primarily considered settings where the constraint set is easy to project onto and does not depend on any unknown parameters. In contrast, this paper focuses on a broader class of misspecified VIs that involve misspecified nonlinear constraints in the primary problem. A detailed comparison between our method and existing approaches is provided in Table 1.

More specifically, we study a coupled VI framework in which the primary VI (Misspecified VI) is defined over a parameter-dependent feasible region $X(\theta)$, specified by a set of convex nonlinear functions. The unknown parameter θ^* is simultaneously estimated by solving a secondary VI problem (2), which we assume to be strongly monotone. To address this problem, we propose a novel

single-loop method that combines augmented Lagrangian and forward-reflected-backward step. To contend with the challenge of misspecified constraints, we show that under suitable assumptions, the corresponding dual iterates remain bounded, which helps us to establish the convergence rate of the proposed method. Furthermore, to measure the quality of the solution, we introduce a *relaxed Minty VI gap* as well as *infeasibility* metrics and establish an ergodic convergence rate of $O(1/K)$ in a monotone setting, matching the optimal first-order convergence rate for fully specified monotone VIs (Juditsky et al. 2011, Nemirovski et al. 2009).

Table 1 Comparison of related misspecified convex optimization/monotone VI studies.

References	Primary problem	Non-linear const.	Misspecif. in const.	Secondary problem	Convergence rate
Ahmadi and Shanbhag (2020)	VI	✗	✗	VI	-
Aybat et al. (2021)	Optimization	✓	✓	Optimization	$O(\log K/K)$
Jiang and Shanbhag (2016)	Stochastic VI	✗	✗	Stochastic VI	$O(\sqrt{\log K}/\sqrt{K})$
Ahmadi and Hamedani (2025)	Saddle Point	✗	✗	Saddle Point	$O(\log K/K)$
This work	VI	✓	✓	VI	$O(1/K)$

1.3. Motivating Example

The Misspecified constrained VIs in problem (Misspecified VI) have broad applications in markets and networked systems where feasibility depends on misspecified parameters learned from data. Some of these examples include constrained Nash-Cournot competition characterized by demand misspecification and policy cap Jiang et al. (2011), inverse and data-driven equilibrium in Thai and Bayen (2018), misspecified Markowitz portfolio optimization problem in Aybat et al. (2021), and minimax schemes with expectation constraints Yang et al. (2025b). Next, we provide a Cournot example in the following motivating example.

Cournot with a price-function constraint and unknown slope: Modern commodity markets often operate under policy rules that constrain prices while firms face uncertainty about demand responsiveness. Consider a homogeneous goods market with N firms, $i = 1, \dots, N$. Firm i chooses a quantity $x_i \geq 0$; let the aggregate output be $X \triangleq \sum_{i=1}^N x_i$. The market clears at a linear inverse demand $p(X; b^*) = a^* - b^*X$, where $a^* > 0$ is known and $b^* > 0$ is the unknown slope capturing how aggressively price falls with output. Firms know costs and capacities but do not know the true b^* . Beyond firm-level capacity limits $x_i \in [0, \text{Cap}_i]$, many markets also face a price-function constraint induced by policy, such as an administrative price cap. We encode this as $p(X; b^*) \leq a^* - \delta$, for some $\delta > 0$. Mathematically, it imposes a lower bound on the feasible output that depends on the (unknown) slope b^* . Let $c_i : [0, \text{Cap}_i] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_+$ be firm i 's convex cost. Then, each firm's objective is to maximize the profit $\pi_i(\mathbf{x}) \triangleq p(X; b^*)x_i - c_i(x_i)$ such that $x_i \in [0, \text{Cap}_i]$ and $p(X; b^*) \leq a^* - \delta$. In practice, the firms observe sample pairs $\{(p_{\text{obs},t}, X_t)\}_{t=1}^T$ and must learn b^* from data while computing equilibria that respect the price constraint.

Formulation as a Misspecified Variational Inequality: We cast the problem as finding a pair (x^*, b^*) in the form of (Misspecified VI) where the secondary VI (2) represents learning parameter b^* from $\{(p_{\text{obs},t}, X_t)\}_{t=1}^T$. For instance, one can use least-squares regression to learn the unknown parameter b^* as follows:

$$b^* = \arg \min_{b \geq 0} \mathcal{L}(b) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{t=1}^T (p_{\text{obs},t} - (a^* - bX_t))^2. \quad (3)$$

Moreover, the feasible set in (Misspecified VI) can be characterized as $\mathcal{X}(b^*) \triangleq \left\{ \mathbf{x} = [x_i]_{i=1}^N \in \prod_{i=1}^N [0, \text{Cap}_i] \mid p(X; b^*) \leq a^* - \delta \right\}$. Then, the operator $F(\mathbf{x}, b)$ is defined by concatenating the gradients of the negative profit functions of the firms $F_i(\mathbf{x}, b) \triangleq c'_i(x_i) + b(X + x_i) - a^*$.

Outline of the paper: The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, we introduce notations and state the assumptions. Section 3 presents the proposed algorithm along with augmented-Lagrangian formulation of the misspecified variational inequality. In Section 4, we establish convergence theory for the proposed method and derive the explicit convergence rate. Section 5 implements a misspecified Cournot equilibrium and empirically compares the proposed scheme against two benchmark methods. Detailed proofs of the lemmas and the theorem are provided in the Appendix.

2. Preliminaries and Assumptions

Notation. Throughout the paper, $\|\cdot\|$ denotes the Euclidean norm, and for any scalar $x \in \mathbb{R}$ we use $[x]_+ \triangleq \max\{x, 0\}$. For a differentiable vector-valued function $f: \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m$, we write $\mathbf{J}f: \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$ for its Jacobian matrix. For a closed convex set X the projection operator is denoted by $\Pi_X(x) \triangleq \arg \min_{y \in X} \|x - y\|$.

We make the following standard assumptions regarding Misspecified VI problem.

ASSUMPTION 1. *The following hold:*

(i) *For any $\theta \in \Theta$, the mapping $F(\cdot, \theta): \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ is continuous and monotone on X , i.e.,*

$$(F(x, \theta) - F(y, \theta))^\top (x - y) \geq 0, \quad \forall x, y \in X.$$

(ii) *The mapping $H: \mathbb{R}^m \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m$ is Lipschitz continuous and strongly monotone on Θ , i.e.,*

$$\|H(\theta) - H(\vartheta)\| \leq L_H \|\theta - \vartheta\|, \quad (H(\theta) - H(\vartheta))^\top (\theta - \vartheta) \geq \mu_H \|\theta - \vartheta\|, \quad \forall \theta, \vartheta \in \Theta.$$

(iii) *For any $j \in \{1, \dots, J\}$ and $\theta \in \Theta$, the function $f_j(\cdot, \theta)$ is convex and continuously differentiable on X . Moreover, there exists $L_{\nabla f, x} \geq 0$ such that for all $x, y \in X$ and all $\theta \in \Theta$,*

$$\|\nabla_x f_j(x, \theta) - \nabla_x f_j(y, \theta)\| \leq L_{\nabla f, x} \|x - y\|.$$

In addition, for any $\theta \in \Theta$ and $x \in X$, $f_j(\cdot, \theta)$ and $f_j(x, \cdot)$ are Lipschitz continuous with constants $L_{f, x} \geq 0$ and $L_{f, \theta} \geq 0$ respectively.

(iv) *The mapping $F: \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^m \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ is Lipschitz continuous in x and θ over $X \times \Theta$; that is, there exist constants $L_{F, x} \geq 0$ and $L_{F, \theta} \geq 0$ such that:*

$$\begin{aligned} \|F(x_1, \theta) - F(x_2, \theta)\| &\leq L_{F, x} \|x_1 - x_2\|, & \forall x_1, x_2 \in X, \quad \forall \theta \in \Theta, \\ \|F(x, \theta_1) - F(x, \theta_2)\| &\leq L_{F, \theta} \|\theta_1 - \theta_2\|, & \forall x \in X, \quad \forall \theta_1, \theta_2 \in \Theta. \end{aligned}$$

(v) *The sets $X \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n$ and $\Theta \subseteq \mathbb{R}^m$ are nonempty, closed, convex and compact.*

(vi) *(Slater's Condition) There exists $\hat{x} \in X$ such that: $f_j(\hat{x}, \theta^*) < 0$, for all $j \in \{1, \dots, J\}$.*

DEFINITION 1. (Augmented-Lagrangian Function for Misspecified VI) For $x, y \in \mathbb{R}^n$, $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}^J$, $\theta \in \mathbb{R}^m$, and $\rho > 0$, the Augmented-Lagrangian function for the Misspecified VI problem is defined as

$$\mathcal{L}_\rho(x, y, \theta, \lambda) \triangleq F(y, \theta)^\top (x - y) + \Phi_\rho(x, \lambda, \theta),$$

where $\Phi_\rho(x, \lambda, \theta) \triangleq \sum_{j=1}^J \phi_\rho(f_j(x, \theta), \lambda_j)$ and $\phi_\rho(u, v) \triangleq \begin{cases} uv + \frac{\rho}{2}u^2, & \text{if } \rho u + v \geq 0, \\ -\frac{v^2}{2\rho}, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$

Based on the above definition, one can observe that

$$\nabla_x \Phi_{\rho_k}(x_k, \lambda_k, \theta^*) = \sum_{j=1}^J \left[\rho_k f_j(x_k, \theta^*) + \lambda_k^{(j)} \right]_+ \nabla f_j(x_k, \theta^*). \quad (4)$$

PROPOSITION 1. (KKT Conditions) Suppose that a solution pair (x^*, θ^*) of (Misspecified VI) exists and Assumption 1 holds. Let $f(x, \theta^*) \triangleq [f_1(x, \theta^*), \dots, f_J(x, \theta^*)]^\top$, and the Jacobian matrix $\nabla f(x, \theta^*) \triangleq [\nabla f_1(x, \theta^*), \dots, \nabla f_J(x, \theta^*)]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times J}$. There exists a pair $(x^*, \theta^*) \in \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^m$ and $\lambda^* \in \mathbb{R}^J$ satisfying the following KKT conditions:

(i) *Stationarity:* $0 \in F(x^*, \theta^*) + \nabla f(x^*, \theta^*)^\top \lambda^* + \mathcal{N}_X(x^*)$ and $0 \in H(\theta^*) + \mathcal{N}_\Theta(\theta^*)$, where $\mathcal{N}_X(x^*)$, and $\mathcal{N}_\Theta(\theta^*)$ are the normal cones of sets X and Θ at x^* and θ^* , respectively.

(ii) *Complementary Slackness:* $0 \leq \lambda^* \perp -f(x^*, \theta^*) \geq 0$.

(iii) *Feasibility:* $x^* \in \mathcal{X}(\theta^*) \triangleq \{x \in X \mid f_j(x, \theta^*) \leq 0, \quad \forall j = 1, \dots, J\}$, and $\theta^* \in \Theta$.

Proof. Note that any solution pair (x^*, θ^*) of (Misspecified VI) is a solution of the following optimization problem

$$\min_{y \in X} y^\top F(x^*, \theta^*) \quad \text{s.t.} \quad f(y, \theta^*) \leq \mathbf{0}. \quad (5)$$

Since the Slater condition holds, the first-order KKT condition of (5) implies that there exists $\lambda^* \in \mathbb{R}^J$ satisfying conditions (i)-(iii). Moreover, the optimality condition of the secondary VI problem (2) immediately implies that $0 \in H(\theta^*) + \mathcal{N}_\Theta(\theta^*)$. \square

LEMMA 1. Consider (Misspecified VI) problem under Assumption 1 and let $(x^*, \theta^*, \lambda^*)$ satisfy the KKT conditions of Proposition 1. Then for all $x \in \mathcal{X}(\theta^*)$, $(x - x^*)^\top F(x^*, \theta^*) + \sum_{j=1}^J \lambda^{*(j)} f_j(x, \theta^*) \geq 0$.

Proof The result follows directly from Lemma 1 in Alizadeh et al. (2024), which establishes the corresponding inequality under Assumption 1. \square

3. Proposed Method

In this section, we present an augmented Lagrangian method for solving (Misspecified VI). Due to the presence of a nonlinear misspecified constraint, we introduce a multiplier λ to relax this constraint, following Definition 1. Moreover, to handle the parameter misspecification, we simultaneously solve a secondary VI problem that generates a sequence of iterates converging to the unique optimal parameter θ^* . The approximation of θ^* obtained at each iteration is then used to update both the main decision variable x and the multiplier λ . To evaluate the quality of the obtained solution, we introduce a *relaxed gap function*. First, recall that the standard VI gap function for (Misspecified VI) is defined as $\text{Gap}(x, \theta^*) \triangleq \sup_{y \in \mathcal{X}(\theta^*)} F(y, \theta^*)^\top (x - y)$, and an ϵ -approximate solution satisfies $\text{Gap}(x, \theta^*) \leq \epsilon$. This gap function is a valid optimality metric, since $\text{Gap}(x, \theta^*) \geq 0$ for any feasible $x \in \mathcal{X}(\theta^*)$, and $\text{Gap}(x, \theta^*) = 0$ implies that x is a solution to (Misspecified VI). However, because our proposed method employs a dual multiplier to enforce constraints and accounts for the misspecified parameter θ , the generated sequence may be infeasible. Consequently, the

algorithm's output \bar{x} may not belong to the feasible set $\mathcal{X}(\theta^*)$, and we might have $\text{Gap}(\bar{x}, \theta^*) < 0$. To address this issue, we measure both (i) the level of *infeasibility*, quantified as $\mathbf{1}^\top [f(x, \theta^*)]_+ \leq \epsilon$, and (ii) a *relaxed gap function* defined as $\widetilde{\text{Gap}}(x, \theta^*) \triangleq \sup_{y \in \mathcal{X}_\epsilon(\theta^*)} F(y, \theta^*)^\top (x - y)$ where $\mathcal{X}_\epsilon(\theta^*) \triangleq \{x \in X \mid \mathbf{1}^\top [f(x, \theta^*)]_+ \leq \epsilon\}$ denotes the ϵ -enlargement of the feasible set. It is straightforward to verify that $\widetilde{\text{Gap}}(x, \theta^*) \geq 0$ for any $x \in \mathcal{X}_\epsilon(\theta^*)$, and $\widetilde{\text{Gap}}(x, \theta^*) \geq \text{Gap}(x, \theta^*)$ for any x . Therefore, we define an ϵ -approximate solution $\bar{x} \in X$ if

$$\text{(Relaxed gap): } \widetilde{\text{Gap}}(\bar{x}, \theta^*) \leq \epsilon, \quad \text{(Infasibility): } \mathbf{1}^\top [f(\bar{x}, \theta^*)]_+ \leq \epsilon.$$

Furthermore, as $\epsilon \rightarrow 0$, the point \bar{x} becomes feasible, i.e., $\bar{x} \in \mathcal{X}(\theta^*)$, which implies that $\widetilde{\text{Gap}}(x, \theta^*) = \text{Gap}(x, \theta^*) = 0$, hence, \bar{x} is a solution to (Misspecified VI).

To find such an approximate solution, we propose a novel single-loop algorithm by combining the forward-reflected-backward method with an augmented Lagrangian update. This combination enables us to effectively handle nonlinear constraints under misspecified evaluations of both the operator F and the nonlinear constraint functions f_j 's. Recall the augmented Lagrangian function from Definition 1, then for fixed (θ, λ) , the term $\Phi_\rho(x, \lambda, \theta)$ imposes penalization for violating the constraints $f_j(x, \theta) \leq 0$. In particular, at each iteration $k \geq 0$, the decision variable x is updated using a projected forward operation applied to the augmented Lagrangian function combined with a reflected (correction) step $r_k = F(x_k, \theta_k) - F(x_{k-1}, \theta_{k-1})$ as $x_{k+1} = \Pi_X[x_k - \gamma_k(r_k + \nabla_x \mathcal{L}_{\rho_k}(x_k, \lambda_k, \theta_k))]$. Then, the dual multiplier λ_k is updated via a projected gradient ascent step to promote feasibility based on the newly updated primal variable x_{k+1} . Finally, the misspecified parameter θ_{k+1} is refined by performing one projected gradient step associated with the secondary VI problem (2). The steps of the algorithm are outlined in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1 Augmented Lagrangian Method for Misspecified VI (ALM-Misspecified VI)

- 1: **Input:** $x_0 \in X, \theta_0 \in \Theta, \{\rho_k, \gamma_k, \eta_k\}_{k \geq 0} \subset \mathbb{R}_{++}$.
 - 2: **Initialization:** $x_{-1} \leftarrow x_0, \theta_{-1} \leftarrow \theta_0, \lambda_0 \leftarrow \mathbf{0}$
 - 3: **for** $k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, K - 1$ **do**
 - 4: $r_k \leftarrow F(x_k, \theta_k) - F(x_{k-1}, \theta_{k-1})$
 - 5: $x_{k+1} \leftarrow \Pi_X [x_k - \gamma_k (F(x_k, \theta_k) + r_k + \mathbf{J}f(x_k, \theta_k)[\rho_k f(x_k, \theta_k) + \lambda_k]_+)]$
 - 6: $\lambda_{k+1} \leftarrow [\lambda_k + \rho_k f(x_{k+1}, \theta_k)]_+$
 - 7: $\theta_{k+1} \leftarrow \Pi_\Theta [\theta_k - \eta_k H(\theta_k)]$
 - 8: **end for**
-

4. Convergence Analysis

In this section, we establish the convergence properties of Algorithm 1 under Assumption 1. In particular, through a step-by-step analysis, we demonstrate that our method achieves a convergence rate of $\mathcal{O}(1/K)$ in terms of the relaxed gap and infeasibility metrics. All related proofs are provided in the Appendix.

We begin by showing some preliminary bounds on the difference between the *constraint enforcement term* of the augmented Lagrangian function, $\Phi_{\rho_k}(x_{k+1}, \lambda_k, \theta^*)$, and the corresponding term in the standard Lagrangian, $\sum_{j=1}^J \lambda^{(j)} f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta^*)$.

LEMMA 2. Consider Algorithm 1. Let us define $J_k^+ \triangleq \{j \in [J] : \rho_k f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta_k) + \lambda_k^{(j)} \geq 0\}$ and $J_k^- \triangleq [J] \setminus J_k^+$. Then for any $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}_+^J$, the following inequality holds:

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$$\begin{aligned}
 -\Phi_{\rho_k}(x_{k+1}, \lambda_k, \theta^*) + \sum_{j=1}^J \lambda^{(j)} f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta^*) &\leq \frac{1}{2\rho_k} \left(\|\lambda_k - \lambda\|^2 - \|\lambda_{k+1} - \lambda\|^2 \right) + \frac{J\rho_k}{2} L_{f,\theta}^2 \|\theta_k - \theta^*\|^2 \\
 &+ L_{\lambda\theta}^\Phi \|\lambda_{k+1} - \lambda\| \|\theta_k - \theta^*\| + 2L_{f,\theta}(J\rho_k D_f + \sqrt{J}\|\lambda_k\|) \|\theta_k - \theta^*\|.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof See Appendix A for the proof. \square

Based on the result of Lemma 2, we next establish a one-step bound for the iterates generated by the proposed algorithm.

LEMMA 3 (Lipschitz continuity of $\nabla_x \Phi_\rho(\cdot, \lambda, \theta)$). *Suppose Assumption 1 holds. Then, for every $\rho > 0$, every $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}^J$, and every $\theta \in \Theta$, the mapping $\nabla_x \Phi_\rho(\cdot, \lambda, \theta)$ is Lipschitz continuous on X . In particular, for any $x, y \in X$, $\|\nabla_x \Phi_\rho(x, \lambda, \theta) - \nabla_x \Phi_\rho(y, \lambda, \theta)\| \leq (\rho C_1 + \|\lambda\| C_2) \|x - y\|$, where $C_1 \triangleq \sqrt{J}(L_{\nabla f, x} D_f + L_{f, x} M_{\nabla f})$, $C_2 \triangleq \sqrt{J} L_{\nabla f, x}$, and $D_f \triangleq \sup_{(z, \vartheta) \in X \times \Theta} \|[f(z, \vartheta)]_+\| < \infty$, $M_{\nabla f} \triangleq \sup_{(z, \vartheta) \in X \times \Theta} \|\nabla_x f(z, \vartheta)\| < \infty$.*

Proof See Appendix B for the proof. \square

LEMMA 4 (One-step analysis). *Let $\{(x_k, \lambda_k, \theta_k)\}_{k \geq 0}$ be the sequence generated by Algorithm 1 and suppose Assumption (1) holds. Then, for any $x \in X$, $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}_+^J$, the following inequality holds for any $k \geq 0$,*

$$\begin{aligned}
 (x_{k+1} - x)^\top F(x, \theta^*) + \sum_{j=1}^J \lambda^{(j)} f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta^*) - \Phi_{\rho_k}(x, \lambda_k, \theta^*) \\
 \leq \frac{1}{2\gamma_k} \left(\|x_k - x\|^2 - \|x_{k+1} - x\|^2 \right) + \frac{1}{2\rho_k} \left(\|\lambda_k - \lambda\|^2 - \|\lambda_{k+1} - \lambda\|^2 \right) + \frac{L_{F,\theta}}{2} \|\theta_{k+1} - \theta_k\|^2 \\
 + \left(\frac{\rho_k C_1 + \|\lambda^*\| C_2 + 2L_{F,x} + L_{F,\theta}}{2} - \frac{1}{2\gamma_k} \right) \|x_{k+1} - x_k\|^2 + \frac{C_2}{2} \|\lambda_k - \lambda^*\| \|x_{k+1} - x_k\|^2 \\
 + \langle r_{k+1}, x_{k+1} - x \rangle - \langle r_k, x_k - x \rangle + L_{F,\theta} \|\theta_{k+1} - \theta^*\| \|x_{k+1} - x\| + \frac{J\rho_k}{2} L_{f,\theta}^2 \|\theta_k - \theta^*\|^2 \\
 + L_{x\theta}^\Phi \|\theta_k - \theta^*\| \left(\|x_{k+1} - x_k\| + \|x_k - x\| \right) + \frac{L_{F,x}}{2} \left(\|x_k - x_{k-1}\|^2 - \|x_{k+1} - x_k\|^2 \right) \\
 + \frac{L_{F,\theta}}{2} \left(\|\theta_k - \theta_{k-1}\|^2 - \|\theta_{k+1} - \theta_k\|^2 \right) + L_{\lambda\theta}^\Phi \|\lambda_{k+1} - \lambda\| \|\theta_k - \theta^*\| \\
 + 2L_{f,\theta}(J\rho_k D_f + \sqrt{J}\|\lambda_k\|) \|\theta_k - \theta^*\|,
 \end{aligned}$$

where $r_k = F(x_k, \theta_k) - F(x_{k-1}, \theta_{k-1})$, $\gamma_k > 0$ is the step-size, and $\rho_k > 0$ is the penalty parameter.

Proof See Appendix C for the proof. \square

Note that the last term on the right-hand side of the inequality contains the product $\|\lambda_{k+1} - \lambda\| \|\theta_k - \theta^*\|$. Assuming that the learning iterates $\{\theta_k\}$ are converging to θ^* , this term will be summable only if the dual iterates do not grow. In fact, in the following lemma, we establish that the dual iterates $\{\lambda_k\}_{k \geq 0}$ are bounded.

LEMMA 5 (Boundedness of Dual Iterates). *Suppose Assumption 1 holds, and define $D_X \triangleq \sup_{x \in X} \|x - x^*\| < \infty$ and $D_\Theta \triangleq \sup_{\theta \in \Theta} \|\theta - \theta^*\| < \infty$. Consider Algorithm 1 with constant penalty $\rho_k \equiv \rho > 0$ and primal step-size $\gamma_k \equiv \gamma \in (0, (\rho C_1 + \|\lambda^*\| C_2 + 2L_{F,x} + L_{F,\theta} + C_2 D_\Lambda)^{-1})$ for some $D_\Lambda > 0$ where C_1, C_2 are defined in Lemma 3. Assume that the learning error satisfies $\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \|\theta_k - \theta^*\| < \infty$ and $\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (k+1)^2 \|\theta_k - \theta^*\|^2 < \infty$, and $\rho_k = \rho = \frac{1}{L_{\lambda\theta}^\Phi}$ for all $k \geq 0$. Then the dual sequence $\{\lambda_k\}$ is bounded.*

Proof See Appendix D for the proof. \square

Lemma 5 establishes bounded dual iterates under compactness and summable learning errors when we use a constant primal step-size and a penalty parameter. We adopt this schedule henceforth, which yields a uniform bound $D_\Lambda \triangleq \sup_{k \geq 0} \|\lambda_k - \lambda^*\| < +\infty$. With this standing in place, we now state the main convergence result for the ergodic primal averages.

THEOREM 1 (Convergence Rate). *Suppose Assumption 1 holds, and Algorithm 1 is executed under the conditions of Lemma 5. Then, for the ergodic average $\bar{x}_K = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K x_k$, the following hold:*

(i) (Infeasibility:) $\mathbf{1}^\top [f(\bar{x}_K, \theta^*)]_+ \leq \frac{C_{\text{feas}}}{K}$.

(ii) (Relaxed gap:) $\widetilde{\text{Gap}}(\bar{x}_K, \theta^*) \triangleq \sup_{x \in X_{\epsilon_K}(\theta^*)} F(x, \theta^*)^\top (\bar{x}_K - x) \leq \frac{C'_T + C'_R(x, 0)}{K} + D_\Lambda \frac{C_{\text{feas}}}{K} + \frac{\rho}{2} \left(\frac{C_{\text{feas}}}{K} \right)^2$,

where $C'_T \triangleq \frac{1}{2\gamma} D_X^2 + 2L_{F,\theta} D_X D_\Theta$, $C'_R(x, 0) = \left(L_{F,\theta} D_X + 2L_{x\theta}^\Phi D_X + 2L_{\lambda\theta}^\Phi D_\Lambda + 2L_{f,\theta} (J\rho D_f + \sqrt{J} (D_\Lambda + \|\lambda^*\|)) \right) \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \|\theta_k - \theta^*\| + \left(L_{F,\theta} + \frac{J\rho}{2} L_{f,\theta}^2 \right) \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \|\theta_k - \theta^*\|^2$, and $C_{\text{feas}} = C'_T + \left(L_{F,\theta} D_X + 2L_{x\theta}^\Phi D_X + 2L_{\lambda\theta}^\Phi D_\Lambda + 2L_{f,\theta} (J\rho D_f + \sqrt{J} (D_\Lambda + \|\lambda^*\|)) \right) \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \|\theta_k - \theta^*\| + \left(L_{F,\theta} + \frac{J\rho}{2} L_{f,\theta}^2 \right) \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \|\theta_k - \theta^*\|^2 + \frac{J + \|\lambda_0 - \lambda^*\|^2}{\rho}$.

Proof See Appendix E for the proof. \square

REMARK 1. Based on Assumption 1-(ii), the secondary VI problem (2) has a Lipschitz continuous and strongly monotone operator which implies that the sequence $\{\theta_k\}_{k \geq 0}$ generated by the projected gradient step in line 7 of Algorithm 1 converges to the optimal unique parameter θ^* at a linear convergence rate (e.g. see (Bauschke and Combettes 2011, Proposition 26.16)); hence, the learning error accumulations $\sum_k \|\theta_k - \theta^*\|$ and $\sum_k (k+2)^2 \|\theta_k - \theta^*\|^2$ in the upper bounds of the result of Theorem 1 are finite with a uniform bound. Therefore, the result of Theorem 1 implies that achieving ϵ -infeasibility and ϵ -relaxed gap requires at most running $O(1/\epsilon)$ iterations of Algorithm 1. We finally remark that the update of misspecified parameter θ in the algorithm can be replaced with other methods, such as extra-gradient method, as long as $\theta_k \rightarrow \theta^*$ at a linear rate.

5. Numerical Experiment

In this section, we test the performance of our proposed method by solving the Cournot model described in Section 1.3 and compare with the Tikhonov regularized VI scheme (Jiang et al. 2011, Ahmadi and Shanbhag 2020) and Extragradient method by (Ahmadi and Shanbhag 2020).

We consider a market with N firms, where each firm $i \in \{1, \dots, N\}$ produces D homogeneous products so the total decision variable dimension is $n = ND$. For each product $d = 1, \dots, D$ of firm i , the capacity is $\text{Cap}_i = 5$ and the quadratic cost function $c_i(x_i) = \frac{1}{2} r_i x_i^2 + g_i x_i$ where r_i, g_i

are randomly generated from uniform distributions $U[1, 10]$ and $U[5, 20]$, respectively. Moreover, $p(X; b^*) = a^* - b^* X$ where $X = \sum_{i=1}^N x_i$, we let $a^* = 100$, and b^* is the solution of the least-square minimization (3) with synthetic observations generated from a true model $X_t \sim U[2, 20]$, $p_{\text{obs},t} = a^* - b^* X_t$, for $t = 1, \dots, T = 300$. All the firms should also satisfy the coupling constraint of the form $f(\mathbf{x}, b^*) \triangleq p(X; b^*) - \delta \leq 0$ for some $\delta > 0$.

We implemented our proposed ALM-Misspecified VI method and compare it with the misspecified Tikhonov regularized VI (Jiang et al. 2011, Ahmadi and Shanbhag 2020) and Extragradient (EG) method by (Ahmadi and Shanbhag 2020). For all methods, the misspecified parameter is updated using one projected gradient step at each iteration. To handle the coupling constraint for the other two methods, we employ the Lagrangian reformulation for each player and construct the corresponding VI operator by concatenating all the players' gradient vectors of the Lagrangian function with respect to primal and dual variables. We consider three problem instances with $(N, D) \in \{(50, 5), (50, 10), (100, 10)\}$ and run each method for a sufficiently large number of iterations with constant step-sizes chosen according to the theoretical findings. Figure 1, shows the performance of the methods in terms of the VI gap $\text{Gap}(\bar{x}_K, b^*)$ and infeasibility $\mathbf{1}^\top [f(\bar{x}_K, b^*)]_+$. Our proposed method (ALM-Misspecified VI) exhibits a superior performance across all instances, while the Lagrangian-Tikhonov and EG-Lagrangian baselines converge more slowly and deteriorate more noticeably as (N, D) grow.

Figure 1 Cournot instances with $(N, D) \in \{(50, 5), (50, 10), (100, 10)\}$

Note. The plots show the VI-Gap (left) and infeasibility (right) for ALM-Misspecified VI (solid), Lagrangian-Tikhonov (dashed with circles), and EG-Lagrangian (dotted with crosses).

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Appendix. Technical Proofs

We include here the full proofs of the lemmas and the theorem for completeness.

A. Proof of Lemma 2

Proof Let j be an index in $\{1, \dots, J\}$. For any j^{th} coordinate using Algorithm 1 (line 6), the dual update is $\lambda_{k+1}^{(j)} = \left[\lambda_k^{(j)} + \rho_k f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta_k) \right]_+$, where $[\cdot]_+$ denotes the projection onto \mathbb{R}_+ . We now consider two cases, when f_j 's are active, we have $\lambda_k^{(j)} + \rho_k f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta_k) > 0$. Then the projection acts as the identity, so we have

$$\lambda_{k+1}^{(j)} = \lambda_k^{(j)} + \rho_k f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta_k) \implies \lambda_{k+1}^{(j)} - \lambda_k^{(j)} = \rho_k f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta_k).$$

Recall the definition 1, then we have

$$\left[\nabla_{\lambda} \Phi_{\rho_k}(x_{k+1}, \lambda_k, \theta_k) \right]_j = \begin{cases} f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta_k) & \text{if } \rho_k f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta_k) + \lambda_k^{(j)} \geq 0 \\ -\frac{\lambda_k^{(j)}}{\rho_k} & \text{if } \rho_k f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta_k) + \lambda_k^{(j)} < 0. \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

Thus, we conclude that in the active case $\lambda_{k+1}^{(j)} - \lambda_k^{(j)} = \rho_k \left[\nabla_{\lambda} \Phi_{\rho_k}(x_{k+1}, \lambda_k, \theta_k) \right]_j$. Again, if $f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta_k)$'s are inactive, then we have $\lambda_k^{(j)} + \rho_k f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta_k) < 0$, hence, $f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta_k) < -\frac{\lambda_k^{(j)}}{\rho_k}$. Thus, we have $\rho_k \left[\nabla_{\lambda} \Phi_{\rho_k}(x_{k+1}, \lambda_k, \theta_k) \right]_j = -\lambda_k^{(j)}$. Therefore, in inactive case also we have $\lambda_{k+1}^{(j)} - \lambda_k^{(j)} = \rho_k \left[\nabla_{\lambda} \Phi_{\rho_k}(x_{k+1}, \lambda_k, \theta_k) \right]_j$. Since the above equality holds for both active and inactive cases, we can write in full vector notation that $\lambda_{k+1} - \lambda_k = \rho_k \nabla_{\lambda} \Phi_{\rho_k}(x_{k+1}, \lambda_k, \theta_k)$. Now by adding and subtracting $\nabla_{\lambda} \Phi_{\rho_k}(x_{k+1}, \lambda_k, \theta^*)$, we get

$$\lambda_{k+1} - \lambda_k = \rho_k \left[e_k + \nabla_{\lambda} \Phi_{\rho_k}(x_{k+1}, \lambda_k, \theta^*) \right], \quad (7)$$

where in the last equality, we define $e_k = \nabla_{\lambda} \Phi_{\rho_k}(x_{k+1}, \lambda_k, \theta_k) - \nabla_{\lambda} \Phi_{\rho_k}(x_{k+1}, \lambda_k, \theta^*)$. For any $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}_+^J$, using the three-point identity and dividing both sides by ρ_k we get

$$\frac{1}{\rho_k} (\lambda_{k+1} - \lambda)^\top (\lambda_{k+1} - \lambda_k) = \frac{1}{2\rho_k} \left[\|\lambda_{k+1} - \lambda\|^2 - \|\lambda_k - \lambda\|^2 + \|\lambda_{k+1} - \lambda_k\|^2 \right]. \quad (8)$$

Using the expression in (7) for $\lambda_{k+1} - \lambda_k$, we see

$$\frac{1}{\rho_k} (\lambda_{k+1} - \lambda)^\top (\lambda_{k+1} - \lambda_k) = (\lambda_{k+1} - \lambda)^\top \nabla_{\lambda} \Phi_{\rho_k}(x_{k+1}, \lambda_k, \theta^*) + (\lambda_{k+1} - \lambda)^\top e_k. \quad (9)$$

Notice that, using (8), we can rewrite (9) as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2\rho_k} \|\lambda_{k+1} - \lambda_k\|^2 &= \frac{1}{2\rho_k} \|\lambda_k - \lambda\|^2 - \frac{1}{2\rho_k} \|\lambda_{k+1} - \lambda\|^2 + (\lambda_{k+1} - \lambda)^\top \nabla_{\lambda} \Phi_{\rho_k}(x_{k+1}, \lambda_k, \theta^*) + (\lambda_{k+1} - \lambda)^\top e_k \\ &\leq \frac{1}{2\rho_k} \left(\|\lambda_k - \lambda\|^2 - \|\lambda_{k+1} - \lambda\|^2 \right) + (\lambda_{k+1} - \lambda)^\top \nabla_{\lambda} \Phi_{\rho_k}(x_{k+1}, \lambda_k, \theta^*) \\ &\quad + L_{\lambda\theta}^\Phi \|\lambda_{k+1} - \lambda\| \|\theta_k - \theta^*\|, \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

where the last inequality follows from the fact that $\nabla_{\lambda} \Phi_{\rho_k}(x, \lambda, \theta)$ is Lipschitz continuous in θ with constant $L_{\lambda\theta}^\Phi$. Now let us define the following sets $J_k^+ \triangleq \left\{ j \in [J] : \rho_k f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta_k) + \lambda_k^{(j)} \geq 0 \right\}$ and $J_k^- \triangleq [J] \setminus J_k^+$. For any $j \in J_k^+$, the dual update in Algorithm 1 (line 6) gives

$$\lambda_{k+1}^{(j)} - \lambda_k^{(j)} = \rho_k f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta_k) = \rho_k \left[f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta^*) + (f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta_k) - f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta^*)) \right].$$

Since $a = b + c$, squaring both sides and using the fact that $(b + c)^2 \geq \frac{1}{2}b^2 - c^2$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} (\lambda_{k+1}^{(j)} - \lambda_k^{(j)})^2 &= \rho_k^2 (f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta_k))^2 \\ &\geq \rho_k^2 \left(\frac{1}{2} (f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta^*))^2 - (f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta_k) - f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta^*))^2 \right). \end{aligned}$$

Finally, invoking Lipschitz continuity of $f_j(x, \theta)$ in θ from Assumption 1(iii), we have

$$(\lambda_{k+1}^{(j)} - \lambda_k^{(j)})^2 \geq \rho_k^2 \left[\frac{1}{2} (f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta^*))^2 - L_{f,\theta}^2 \|\theta_k - \theta^*\|^2 \right].$$

Summing over $j \in J_k^+$ and multiplying by $1/(2\rho_k)$, we have

$$\frac{1}{2\rho_k} \sum_{j \in J_k^+} (\lambda_{k+1}^{(j)} - \lambda_k^{(j)})^2 \geq \frac{\rho_k}{4} \sum_{j \in J_k^+} (f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta^*))^2 - \frac{J\rho_k}{2} L_{f,\theta}^2 \|\theta_k - \theta^*\|^2.$$

If $j \in J_k^-$, then $\lambda_{k+1}^{(j)} = 0 \implies (\lambda_{k+1}^{(j)} - \lambda_k^{(j)})^2 = (\lambda_k^{(j)})^2$. Multiplying both sides by $\frac{1}{2\rho_k}$, and combining both of the above inequalities, we get

$$\frac{1}{2\rho_k} \|\lambda_{k+1} - \lambda_k\|^2 \geq \frac{\rho_k}{4} \sum_{j \in J_k^+} (f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta^*))^2 + \frac{1}{2\rho_k} \sum_{j \in J_k^-} (\lambda_k^{(j)})^2 - \frac{J\rho_k}{2} L_{f,\theta}^2 \|\theta_k - \theta^*\|^2.$$

After rearranging, this gives us

$$-\left(\frac{1}{2\rho_k} \|\lambda_{k+1} - \lambda_k\|^2 + \frac{J\rho_k}{2} L_{f,\theta}^2 \|\theta_k - \theta^*\|^2 \right) \leq -\left[\frac{\rho_k}{4} \sum_{j \in J_k^+} (f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta^*))^2 + \frac{1}{2\rho_k} \sum_{j \in J_k^-} (\lambda_k^{(j)})^2 \right]. \quad (11)$$

Now, notice that

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi_{\rho_k}(x_{k+1}, \lambda_k, \theta^*) &= \Phi_{\rho_k}(x_{k+1}, \lambda_k, \theta^*) - \Phi_{\rho_k}(x_{k+1}, \lambda_k, \theta_k) + \Phi_{\rho_k}(x_{k+1}, \lambda_k, \theta_k) \\ &= \sum_{j \in J_k^+} \left(\frac{\rho_k}{2} (f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta_k))^2 + \lambda_k^{(j)} f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta_k) \right) - \sum_{j \in J_k^-} \frac{(\lambda_k^{(j)})^2}{2\rho_k} \\ &\quad + \Phi_{\rho_k}(x_{k+1}, \lambda_k, \theta^*) - \Phi_{\rho_k}(x_{k+1}, \lambda_k, \theta_k). \end{aligned}$$

For each $j \in J_k^+$, we add and subtract the term $\frac{\rho_k}{2} (f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta^*))^2 + \lambda_k^{(j)} f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta^*)$ inside the summation, hence we obtain

$$\Phi_{\rho_k}(x_{k+1}, \lambda_k, \theta^*) = \sum_{j \in J_k^+} \left(\frac{\rho_k}{2} (f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta^*))^2 + \lambda_k^{(j)} f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta^*) \right) - \sum_{j \in J_k^-} \frac{(\lambda_k^{(j)})^2}{2\rho_k} + E_k, \quad (12)$$

where $E_k \triangleq \sum_{j \in J_k^+} \left(\frac{\rho_k}{2} ((f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta_k))^2 - (f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta^*))^2) + \lambda_k^{(j)} (f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta_k) - f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta^*)) \right) + \Phi_{\rho_k}(x_{k+1}, \lambda_k, \theta^*) - \Phi_{\rho_k}(x_{k+1}, \lambda_k, \theta_k)$. Now using the facts from (6) and (12), we can expand as follows

$$\begin{aligned} & \Phi_{\rho_k}(x_{k+1}, \lambda_k, \theta^*) - \sum_{j=1}^J \lambda^{(j)} f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta^*) - (\lambda_{k+1} - \lambda)^\top \nabla \lambda \Phi_{\rho_k}(x_{k+1}, \lambda_k, \theta^*) \\ &= \sum_{j \in J_k^+} \left(\frac{\rho_k}{2} (f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta^*))^2 + \lambda_k^{(j)} f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta^*) \right) - \sum_{j \in J_k^-} \frac{(\lambda_k^{(j)})^2}{2\rho_k} - \sum_{j \in J_k^+} (\lambda_{k+1}^{(j)} - \lambda^{(j)}) f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta^*) \\ & \quad - \sum_{j \in J_k^-} (\lambda_{k+1}^{(j)} - \lambda^{(j)}) \left(-\frac{\lambda_k^{(j)}}{\rho_k} \right) - \sum_{j \in J_k^+} \lambda^{(j)} f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta^*) - \sum_{j \in J_k^-} \lambda^{(j)} f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta^*) + E_k. \end{aligned}$$

Next, by grouping the positive and negative index sets on the RHS separately, we get

$$\begin{aligned} &= \sum_{j \in J_k^+} \left(\frac{\rho_k}{2} (f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta^*))^2 + \lambda_k^{(j)} f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta^*) \right) - \sum_{j \in J_k^-} \frac{(\lambda_k^{(j)})^2}{2\rho_k} - \sum_{j \in J_k^-} \lambda^{(j)} f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta^*) \\ & \quad - \sum_{j \in J_k^+} \left(\lambda_k^{(j)} + \rho_k f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta^*) - \lambda^{(j)} \right) f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta^*) - \sum_{j \in J_k^-} \left(-\lambda^{(j)} \right) \left(-\frac{\lambda_k^{(j)}}{\rho_k} \right) - \sum_{j \in J_k^+} \lambda^{(j)} f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta^*) + E_k. \end{aligned}$$

Now, observe that the terms inside the sum over J_k^+ can be combined, since both involve $f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta^*)$. After cancellation we arrive at

$$\begin{aligned} &= \sum_{j \in J_k^+} \left[\frac{\rho_k}{2} (f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta^*))^2 + \lambda_k^{(j)} f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta^*) - \lambda^{(j)} f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta^*) \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \left(\lambda_k^{(j)} + \rho_k f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta^*) - \lambda^{(j)} \right) f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta^*) \right] - \sum_{j \in J_k^-} \left(\frac{(\lambda_k^{(j)})^2}{2\rho_k} + \lambda^{(j)} \left(f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta^*) + \frac{\lambda_k^{(j)}}{\rho_k} \right) \right) + E_k. \end{aligned}$$

Finally, simplifying the quadratic terms in $f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta^*)$, we can conclude that

$$\begin{aligned} & \Phi_{\rho_k}(x_{k+1}, \lambda_k, \theta^*) - \sum_{j=1}^J \lambda^{(j)} f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta^*) - (\lambda_{k+1} - \lambda)^\top \nabla \lambda \Phi_{\rho_k}(x_{k+1}, \lambda_k, \theta^*) \\ &= - \sum_{j \in J_k^+} \frac{\rho_k}{2} (f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta^*))^2 - \sum_{j \in J_k^-} \left(\frac{(\lambda_k^{(j)})^2}{2\rho_k} + \lambda^{(j)} \left(f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta^*) + \frac{\lambda_k^{(j)}}{\rho_k} \right) \right) + E_k. \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Note that, for any $\lambda^{(j)} \geq 0$ and $\forall j \in J_k^-$, we have $\left(f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta^*) + \frac{\lambda_k^{(j)}}{\rho_k} \right) \leq 0$. Then from (13), we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \Phi_{\rho_k}(x_{k+1}, \lambda_k, \theta^*) - \sum_{j=1}^J \lambda^{(j)} f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta^*) - (\lambda_{k+1} - \lambda)^\top \nabla \lambda \Phi_{\rho_k}(x_{k+1}, \lambda_k, \theta^*) \\ & \geq - \left(\sum_{j \in J_k^+} \frac{\rho_k}{2} (f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta^*))^2 + \sum_{j \in J_k^-} \frac{(\lambda_k^{(j)})^2}{2\rho_k} \right) + E_k \\ & \geq - \left(\frac{1}{2\rho_k} \|\lambda_{k+1} - \lambda_k\|^2 + \frac{J\rho_k}{2} L_{f,\theta}^2 \|\theta_k - \theta^*\|^2 \right) + E_k, \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

where the last inequality follows from (11). Therefore, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 & -\Phi_{\rho_k}(x_{k+1}, \lambda_k, \theta^*) + \sum_{j=1}^J \lambda^{(j)} f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta^*) + (\lambda_{k+1} - \lambda)^\top \nabla \Phi_{\rho_k}(x_{k+1}, \lambda_k, \theta^*) \\
 & \leq \left(\frac{1}{2\rho_k} \|\lambda_{k+1} - \lambda_k\|^2 + \frac{J\rho_k}{2} L_{f,\theta}^2 \|\theta_k - \theta^*\|^2 \right) - E_k.
 \end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

Recall that $E_k = \sum_{j \in J_k^+} \left(\frac{\rho_k}{2} (f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta_k)^2 - f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta^*)^2) + \lambda_k^{(j)} (f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta_k) - f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta^*)) \right) + \Phi_{\rho_k}(x_{k+1}, \lambda_k, \theta^*) - \Phi_{\rho_k}(x_{k+1}, \lambda_k, \theta_k)$. Using the triangle inequality and $a^2 - b^2 = (a - b)(a + b)$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 |E_k| & \leq \sum_{j \in J_k^+} \frac{\rho_k}{2} |f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta_k) - f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta^*)| |f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta_k) + f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta^*)| \\
 & \quad + \sum_{j \in J_k^+} |\lambda_k^{(j)}| |f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta_k) - f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta^*)| + |\Phi_{\rho_k}(x_{k+1}, \lambda_k, \theta^*) - \Phi_{\rho_k}(x_{k+1}, \lambda_k, \theta_k)|.
 \end{aligned} \tag{16}$$

Recall that $\Phi_\rho(x, \lambda, \theta) = \sum_{j=1}^J \phi_\rho(f_j(x, \theta), \lambda_j)$, moreover, one can observe that for any $u_j, u'_j \in \mathbb{R}$, $|\phi_\rho(u_j, v_j) - \phi_\rho(u'_j, v_j)| \leq (|v_j| + \rho D_f) |u_j - u'_j|$. Therefore, by Lipschitz continuity of $f_j(x, \theta)$ in θ we conclude that for any $\theta, \theta' \in \Theta$, $|\phi_\rho(f_j(x, \theta), \lambda^{(j)}) - \phi_\rho(f_j(x, \theta'), \lambda^{(j)})| \leq (|\lambda^{(j)}| + \rho D_f) L_{f,\theta} \|\theta - \theta'\|$ which summing over j implies that

$$|\Phi_\rho(x, \lambda, \theta) - \Phi_\rho(x, \lambda, \theta')| \leq L_{f,\theta} (J\rho D_f + \sqrt{J} \|\lambda\|) \|\theta - \theta'\|. \tag{17}$$

Using the above inequality within (16) and by Lipschitz continuity of $f_j(x, \theta)$ in θ and the bound $|f_j(x, \theta)| \leq D_f$, we conclude that

$$|E_k| \leq 2L_{f,\theta} (J\rho_k D_f + \sqrt{J} \|\lambda_k\|) \|\theta_k - \theta^*\|. \tag{18}$$

Now using (10) and (18) in (15), we can show

$$\begin{aligned}
 -\Phi_{\rho_k}(x_{k+1}, \lambda_k, \theta^*) + \sum_{j=1}^J \lambda^{(j)} f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta^*) & \leq \frac{1}{2\rho_k} \left(\|\lambda_k - \lambda\|^2 - \|\lambda_{k+1} - \lambda\|^2 \right) + L_{\lambda\theta}^\Phi \|\lambda_{k+1} - \lambda\| \|\theta_k - \theta^*\| \\
 & \quad + \frac{J\rho_k}{2} L_{f,\theta}^2 \|\theta_k - \theta^*\|^2 + 2L_{f,\theta} (J\rho_k D_f + \sqrt{J} \|\lambda_k\|) \|\theta_k - \theta^*\|. \quad \square \tag{19}
 \end{aligned}$$

B. Proof of Lemma 3

Proof Recall from Definition 1 and (4), for any $x \in X$, we have

$$\nabla_x \Phi_\rho(x, \lambda, \theta) = \sum_{j=1}^J [\rho f_j(x, \theta) + \lambda^{(j)}]_+ \nabla_x f_j(x, \theta) = \nabla_x f(x, \theta)^\top [\rho f(x, \theta) + \lambda]_+.$$

Fix $\rho > 0$, $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}^J$, and $\theta \in \Theta$. Then for any $x, y \in X$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 \nabla_x \Phi_\rho(x, \lambda, \theta) - \nabla_x \Phi_\rho(y, \lambda, \theta) & = \nabla_x f(x, \theta)^\top [\rho f(x, \theta) + \lambda]_+ - \nabla_x f(y, \theta)^\top [\rho f(y, \theta) + \lambda]_+ \\
 & = (\nabla_x f(x, \theta) - \nabla_x f(y, \theta))^\top [\rho f(x, \theta) + \lambda]_+ \\
 & \quad + \nabla_x f(y, \theta)^\top \left([\rho f(x, \theta) + \lambda]_+ - [\rho f(y, \theta) + \lambda]_+ \right),
 \end{aligned}$$

where we added and subtracted $\nabla_x f(y, \theta)^\top [\rho f(x, \theta) + \lambda]_+$. Taking norms and applying the triangle inequality yields

$$\begin{aligned} \|\nabla_x \Phi_\rho(x, \lambda, \theta) - \nabla_x \Phi_\rho(y, \lambda, \theta)\| &\leq \|\nabla_x f(x, \theta) - \nabla_x f(y, \theta)\| \|[\rho f(x, \theta) + \lambda]_+\| \\ &\quad + \|\nabla_x f(y, \theta)\| \|[\rho f(x, \theta) + \lambda]_+ - [\rho f(y, \theta) + \lambda]_+\|. \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

Since $[\cdot]_+$ is the projection onto \mathbb{R}_+^J , it is non-expansive. Therefore,

$$\|f(x, \theta) - f(y, \theta)\| = \left(\sum_{j=1}^J |f_j(x, \theta) - f_j(y, \theta)|^2 \right)^{1/2} \leq \sqrt{J} L_{f,x} \|x - y\|.$$

Consequently, it follows that

$$\|[\rho f(x, \theta) + \lambda]_+ - [\rho f(y, \theta) + \lambda]_+\| \leq \rho \sqrt{J} L_{f,x} \|x - y\|.$$

Similarly, by Assumption 1(iii), each $\nabla_x f_j(\cdot, \theta)$ is Lipschitz continuous in x with constant $L_{\nabla f,x}$. Therefore, the Jacobian matrix satisfies

$$\|\nabla_x f(x, \theta) - \nabla_x f(y, \theta)\| \leq \sqrt{J} L_{\nabla f,x} \|x - y\|.$$

Substituting these bounds into (20), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \|\nabla_x \Phi_\rho(x, \lambda, \theta) - \nabla_x \Phi_\rho(y, \lambda, \theta)\| &\leq \sqrt{J} L_{\nabla f,x} \|x - y\| \|[\rho f(x, \theta) + \lambda]_+\| \\ &\quad + \rho \sqrt{J} L_{f,x} \|x - y\| \|\nabla_x f(y, \theta)\|. \end{aligned}$$

Now, since $X \times \Theta$ is compact and the mappings $(z, \theta) \mapsto f(z, \theta)$ and $(z, \theta) \mapsto \nabla_x f(z, \theta)$ are continuous, the quantities $D_f \triangleq \sup_{(z, \theta) \in X \times \Theta} \| [f(z, \theta)]_+ \| < \infty$, $M_{\nabla f} \triangleq \sup_{(z, \theta) \in X \times \Theta} \|\nabla_x f(z, \theta)\| < \infty$, are well defined and finite. Moreover, $\|[\rho f(x, \theta) + \lambda]_+\| \leq \rho \| [f(x, \theta)]_+ \| + \|\lambda\| \leq \rho D_f + \|\lambda\|$, and $\|\nabla_x f(y, \theta)\| \leq M_{\nabla f}$. Hence, we get

$$\|\nabla_x \Phi_\rho(x, \lambda, \theta) - \nabla_x \Phi_\rho(y, \lambda, \theta)\| \leq \sqrt{J} L_{\nabla f,x} (\rho D_f + \|\lambda\|) \|x - y\| + \rho \sqrt{J} L_{f,x} M_{\nabla f} \|x - y\|.$$

Rearranging terms gives

$$\|\nabla_x \Phi_\rho(x, \lambda, \theta) - \nabla_x \Phi_\rho(y, \lambda, \theta)\| \leq (\rho C_1 + \|\lambda\| C_2) \|x - y\|,$$

where $C_1 \triangleq \sqrt{J} (L_{\nabla f,x} D_f + L_{f,x} M_{\nabla f})$, $C_2 \triangleq \sqrt{J} L_{\nabla f,x}$. Thus, $\nabla_x \Phi_\rho(\cdot, \lambda, \theta)$ is Lipschitz continuous on X . \square

C. Proof of Lemma 4

Proof Let $x \in X$ and $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}_+^J$ be arbitrary vectors. From Algorithm 1 (line 5) we have:

$$(x_{k+1} - x)^\top \left(x_{k+1} - x_k + \gamma_k \left(F(x_k, \theta_k) + r_k + \mathbf{J}f(x_k, \theta_k) \left[\rho_k f(x_k, \theta_k) + \lambda_k \right]_+ \right) \right) \leq 0. \quad (21)$$

Considering (21), to find a lower bound for $(x_{k+1} - x)^\top (F(x_k, \theta_k) + r_k)$, we add and subtract $(x_{k+1} - x)^\top F(x_{k+1}, \theta_{k+1})$, obtaining:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & (x_{k+1} - x)^\top (F(x_k, \theta_k) + r_k) \pm (x_{k+1} - x)^\top F(x_{k+1}, \theta_{k+1}) \\
 &= \langle r_k, x_k - x \rangle - \langle r_{k+1}, x_{k+1} - x \rangle + \langle r_k, x_{k+1} - x_k \rangle + \langle F(x_{k+1}, \theta_{k+1}), x_{k+1} - x \rangle \\
 &= (x_{k+1} - x)^\top (F(x_{k+1}, \theta^*) + [F(x_{k+1}, \theta_{k+1}) - F(x_{k+1}, \theta^*)]) + \langle r_k, x_k - x \rangle \\
 &\quad - \langle r_{k+1}, x_{k+1} - x \rangle + \langle r_k, x_{k+1} - x_k \rangle \\
 &\geq (x_{k+1} - x)^\top F(x, \theta^*) + (x_{k+1} - x)^\top [F(x_{k+1}, \theta_{k+1}) - F(x_{k+1}, \theta^*)] + \langle r_k, x_k - x \rangle \\
 &\quad - \langle r_{k+1}, x_{k+1} - x \rangle + \langle r_k, x_{k+1} - x_k \rangle,
 \end{aligned}$$

where in the last inequality, we use the monotonicity of $F(\cdot, \theta^*)$. Next, using Cauchy-Schwarz inequality and Lipschitz continuity of $F(x, \cdot)$ with respect to θ , we can show:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & (x_{k+1} - x)^\top (F(x_k, \theta_k) + r_k) \\
 &\geq (x_{k+1} - x)^\top F(x, \theta^*) - \left(L_{F,x} \|x_k - x_{k-1}\| + L_{F,\theta} \|\theta_k - \theta_{k-1}\| \right) \|x_{k+1} - x_k\| \\
 &\quad - L_{F,\theta} \|\theta_{k+1} - \theta^*\| \|x_{k+1} - x\| + \langle r_k, x_k - x \rangle - \langle r_{k+1}, x_{k+1} - x \rangle
 \end{aligned} \tag{22}$$

Taking into account 4, by adding and subtracting $\nabla_x \Phi_{\rho_k}(x_k, \lambda_k, \theta^*)$, we can obtain the following.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & (x_{k+1} - x)^\top \mathbf{J}f(x_k, \theta_k) \left[\rho_k f(x_k, \theta_k) + \lambda_k \right]_+ \\
 &= (x_{k+1} - x_k)^\top \nabla_x \Phi_{\rho_k}(x_k, \lambda_k, \theta_k) + (x_k - x)^\top \nabla_x \Phi_{\rho_k}(x_k, \lambda_k, \theta_k) \\
 &= (x_{k+1} - x_k)^\top \left(\nabla_x \Phi_{\rho_k}(x_k, \lambda_k, \theta^*) + [\nabla_x \Phi_{\rho_k}(x_k, \lambda_k, \theta_k) - \nabla_x \Phi_{\rho_k}(x_k, \lambda_k, \theta^*)] \right) \\
 &\quad + (x_k - x)^\top \left(\nabla_x \Phi_{\rho_k}(x_k, \lambda_k, \theta^*) + [\nabla_x \Phi_{\rho_k}(x_k, \lambda_k, \theta_k) - \nabla_x \Phi_{\rho_k}(x_k, \lambda_k, \theta^*)] \right) \\
 &\geq (x_{k+1} - x_k)^\top \nabla_x \Phi_{\rho_k}(x_k, \lambda_k, \theta^*) + (x_{k+1} - x_k)^\top [\nabla_x \Phi_{\rho_k}(x_k, \lambda_k, \theta_k) - \nabla_x \Phi_{\rho_k}(x_k, \lambda_k, \theta^*)] \\
 &\quad + \Phi_{\rho_k}(x_k, \lambda_k, \theta^*) - \Phi_{\rho_k}(x_k, \lambda_k, \theta_k) + (x_k - x)^\top [\nabla_x \Phi_{\rho_k}(x_k, \lambda_k, \theta_k) - \nabla_x \Phi_{\rho_k}(x_k, \lambda_k, \theta^*)],
 \end{aligned}$$

where in the last inequality, we use the convexity of $\Phi_{\rho_k}(\cdot, \lambda_k, \theta^*)$. Next, using the Cauchy-Schwarz inequality and Lipschitz continuity of $\nabla_x \Phi_{\rho_k}(x, \lambda, \cdot)$ with respect θ with a constant $L_{x\theta}^\Phi$, we can show

$$\begin{aligned}
 & (x_{k+1} - x)^\top \mathbf{J}f(x_k, \theta_k) \left[\rho_k f(x_k, \theta_k) + \lambda_k \right]_+ \geq (x_{k+1} - x_k)^\top \nabla_x \Phi_{\rho_k}(x_k, \lambda_k, \theta^*) \\
 &\quad + \Phi_{\rho_k}(x_k, \lambda_k, \theta^*) - \Phi_{\rho_k}(x_k, \lambda_k, \theta_k) - L_{x\theta}^\Phi \|\theta_k - \theta^*\| \left(\|x_{k+1} - x_k\| + \|x_k - x\| \right).
 \end{aligned} \tag{23}$$

Moreover, using the three-point equality, we can write:

$$(x_{k+1} - x)^\top (x_{k+1} - x_k) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\|x_{k+1} - x\|^2 - \|x_k - x\|^2 + \|x_{k+1} - x_k\|^2 \right). \tag{24}$$

Using (22), (23), and (24) in (21), we have:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & (x_{k+1} - x)^\top F(x, \theta^*) + \Phi_{\rho_k}(x_k, \lambda_k, \theta^*) - \Phi_{\rho_k}(x, \lambda_k, \theta^*) \\
 & \leq \frac{1}{2\gamma_k} \left(\|x_k - x\|^2 - \|x_{k+1} - x\|^2 - \|x_{k+1} - x_k\|^2 \right) - (x_{k+1} - x_k)^\top \nabla_x \Phi_{\rho_k}(x_k, \lambda_k, \theta^*) \\
 & \quad + L_{F,\theta} \|\theta_{k+1} - \theta^*\| \|x_{k+1} - x\| + L_{x\theta}^\Phi \|\theta_k - \theta^*\| \left(\|x_{k+1} - x_k\| + \|x_k - x\| \right) \\
 & \quad + \|x_{k+1} - x_k\| \left(L_{F,x} \|x_k - x_{k-1}\| + L_{F,\theta} \|\theta_k - \theta_{k-1}\| \right) + \langle r_{k+1}, x_{k+1} - x \rangle - \langle r_k, x_k - x \rangle. \tag{25}
 \end{aligned}$$

Next, using the Lemma 3, we have $\Phi_{\rho_k}(x_{k+1}, \lambda_k, \theta^*) \leq \Phi_{\rho_k}(x_k, \lambda_k, \theta^*) + \langle \nabla_x \Phi_{\rho_k}(x_k, \lambda_k, \theta^*), x_{k+1} - x_k \rangle + \frac{\rho_k C_1 + \|\lambda_k\| C_2}{2} \|x_{k+1} - x_k\|^2$. Substituting this estimate into (25) yields

$$\begin{aligned}
 & (x_{k+1} - x)^\top F(x, \theta^*) + \Phi_{\rho_k}(x_{k+1}, \lambda_k, \theta^*) - \Phi_{\rho_k}(x, \lambda_k, \theta^*) \\
 & \leq \frac{1}{2\gamma_k} \left(\|x_k - x\|^2 - \|x_{k+1} - x\|^2 - \|x_{k+1} - x_k\|^2 \right) + \langle r_{k+1}, x_{k+1} - x \rangle - \langle r_k, x_k - x \rangle \\
 & \quad + L_{F,\theta} \|\theta_{k+1} - \theta^*\| \|x_{k+1} - x\| + L_{x\theta}^\Phi \|\theta_k - \theta^*\| \left(\|x_{k+1} - x_k\| + \|x_k - x\| \right) \\
 & \quad + \frac{\rho_k C_1 + \|\lambda_k\| C_2}{2} \|x_{k+1} - x_k\|^2 + \|x_{k+1} - x_k\| \left(L_{F,x} \|x_k - x_{k-1}\| + L_{F,\theta} \|\theta_k - \theta_{k-1}\| \right). \tag{26}
 \end{aligned}$$

To treat the term involving $\|\lambda_k\|$, we first add and subtract λ^* inside the norm and use the triangle inequality to obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{\rho_k C_1 + \|\lambda_k\| C_2}{2} \|x_{k+1} - x_k\|^2 &= \left(\frac{\rho_k C_1 + \|\lambda^* + (\lambda_k - \lambda^*)\| C_2}{2} \right) \|x_{k+1} - x_k\|^2 \\
 &\leq \frac{\rho_k C_1 + \|\lambda^*\| C_2}{2} \|x_{k+1} - x_k\|^2 + \frac{C_2}{2} \|\lambda_k - \lambda^*\| \|x_{k+1} - x_k\|^2. \tag{27}
 \end{aligned}$$

Using (19) from Lemma (2) and substituting (27) into (26), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 & (x_{k+1} - x)^\top F(x, \theta^*) + \sum_{j=1}^J \lambda^{(j)} f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta^*) - \Phi_{\rho_k}(x, \lambda_k, \theta^*) \\
 & \leq \frac{1}{2\gamma_k} \left(\|x_k - x\|^2 - \|x_{k+1} - x\|^2 - \|x_{k+1} - x_k\|^2 \right) + \langle r_{k+1}, x_{k+1} - x \rangle - \langle r_k, x_k - x \rangle + \frac{J\rho_k}{2} L_{f,\theta}^2 \|\theta_k - \theta^*\|^2 \\
 & \quad + L_{F,\theta} \|\theta_{k+1} - \theta^*\| \|x_{k+1} - x\| + L_{x\theta}^\Phi \|\theta_k - \theta^*\| \left(\|x_{k+1} - x_k\| + \|x_k - x\| \right) + L_{\lambda\theta}^\Phi \|\lambda_{k+1} - \lambda\| \|\theta_k - \theta^*\| \\
 & \quad + \|x_{k+1} - x_k\| \left(L_{F,x} \|x_k - x_{k-1}\| + L_{F,\theta} \|\theta_k - \theta_{k-1}\| \right) + \frac{1}{2\rho_k} \left(\|\lambda_k - \lambda\|^2 - \|\lambda_{k+1} - \lambda\|^2 \right) \\
 & \quad + \frac{\rho_k C_1 + \|\lambda^*\| C_2}{2} \|x_{k+1} - x_k\|^2 + \frac{C_2}{2} \|\lambda_k - \lambda^*\| \|x_{k+1} - x_k\|^2 + 2L_{f,\theta} (J\rho_k D_f + \sqrt{J}\|\lambda_k\|) \|\theta_k - \theta^*\|. \tag{28}
 \end{aligned}$$

Note that applying Young's inequality to the term $\|x_{k+1} - x_k\| \left(L_{F,x} \|x_k - x_{k-1}\| + L_{F,\theta} \|\theta_k - \theta_{k-1}\| \right)$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \|x_{k+1} - x_k\| \left(L_{F,x} \|x_k - x_{k-1}\| + L_{F,\theta} \|\theta_k - \theta_{k-1}\| \right) \\
 & \leq \frac{L_{F,x}}{2} \|x_{k+1} - x_k\|^2 + \frac{L_{F,x}}{2} \|x_k - x_{k-1}\|^2 + \frac{L_{F,\theta}}{2} \|x_{k+1} - x_k\|^2 + \frac{L_{F,\theta}}{2} \|\theta_k - \theta_{k-1}\|^2 \\
 & = \left(\frac{L_{F,x} + L_{F,\theta}}{2} \right) \|x_{k+1} - x_k\|^2 + \frac{L_{F,x}}{2} \|x_k - x_{k-1}\|^2 + \frac{L_{F,\theta}}{2} \|\theta_k - \theta_{k-1}\|^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Now let us add and subtract $\frac{L_{F,x}}{2} \|x_{k+1} - x_k\|^2$ and $\frac{L_{F,\theta}}{2} \|\theta_{k+1} - \theta_k\|^2$ with the respective terms to obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\frac{L_{F,x} + L_{F,\theta}}{2} \right) \|x_{k+1} - x_k\|^2 + \frac{L_{F,x}}{2} \|x_k - x_{k-1}\|^2 + \frac{L_{F,\theta}}{2} \|\theta_k - \theta_{k-1}\|^2 \\ &= \left(\frac{2L_{F,x} + L_{F,\theta}}{2} \right) \|x_{k+1} - x_k\|^2 + \frac{L_{F,\theta}}{2} \|\theta_{k+1} - \theta_k\|^2 \\ & \quad + \frac{L_{F,x}}{2} \left(\|x_k - x_{k-1}\|^2 - \|x_{k+1} - x_k\|^2 \right) + \frac{L_{F,\theta}}{2} \left(\|\theta_k - \theta_{k-1}\|^2 - \|\theta_{k+1} - \theta_k\|^2 \right). \end{aligned}$$

Putting all terms together in (28), we get

ATTENTION: The following displayed equation, in its current form, exceeds the column width that will be used in the published edition of your article. Please break or rewrite this equation to fit, including the equation number, within a column width of 470 pt / 165.81 mm / 6.53 in (the width of this red box).

$$\begin{aligned} & (x_{k+1} - x)^\top F(x, \theta^*) + \sum_{j=1}^J \lambda^{(j)} f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta^*) - \Phi_{\rho_k}(x, \lambda_k, \theta^*) \\ & \leq \frac{1}{2\gamma_k} \left(\|x_k - x\|^2 - \|x_{k+1} - x\|^2 \right) + \frac{1}{2\rho_k} \left(\|\lambda_k - \lambda\|^2 - \|\lambda_{k+1} - \lambda\|^2 \right) + \frac{J\rho_k}{2} L_{f,\theta}^2 \|\theta_k - \theta^*\|^2 \\ & \quad + \left(\frac{\rho_k C_1 + \|\lambda^*\| C_2 + 2L_{F,x} + L_{F,\theta}}{2} - \frac{1}{2\gamma_k} \right) \|x_{k+1} - x_k\|^2 + \frac{C_2}{2} \|\lambda_k - \lambda^*\| \|x_{k+1} - x_k\|^2 + \frac{L_{F,\theta}}{2} \|\theta_{k+1} - \theta_k\|^2 \\ & \quad + \langle r_{k+1}, x_{k+1} - x \rangle - \langle r_k, x_k - x \rangle + L_{F,\theta} \|\theta_{k+1} - \theta^*\| \|x_{k+1} - x\| + L_{x\theta}^\Phi \|\theta_k - \theta^*\| \left(\|x_{k+1} - x_k\| + \|x_k - x\| \right) \\ & \quad + \frac{L_{F,x}}{2} \left(\|x_k - x_{k-1}\|^2 - \|x_{k+1} - x_k\|^2 \right) + \frac{L_{F,\theta}}{2} \left(\|\theta_k - \theta_{k-1}\|^2 - \|\theta_{k+1} - \theta_k\|^2 \right) \\ & \quad + L_{\lambda\theta}^\Phi \|\lambda_{k+1} - \lambda\| \|\theta_k - \theta^*\| + 2L_{f,\theta} (J\rho_k D_f + \sqrt{J} \|\lambda_k\|) \|\theta_k - \theta^*\|. \quad \square \end{aligned} \tag{29}$$

D. Proof of Lemma 5

Proof From (29), setting $(x, \lambda) = (x^*, \lambda^*)$ gives, for all $k \geq 0$

$$\begin{aligned} 0 & \leq \frac{1}{2\gamma_k} \left(\|x_k - x^*\|^2 - \|x_{k+1} - x^*\|^2 \right) + \frac{1}{2\rho_k} \left(\|\lambda_k - \lambda^*\|^2 - \|\lambda_{k+1} - \lambda^*\|^2 \right) + \frac{L_{F,\theta}}{2} \|\theta_{k+1} - \theta_k\|^2 \\ & \quad + \left(\frac{\rho_k C_1 + \|\lambda^*\| C_2 + 2L_{F,x} + L_{F,\theta}}{2} - \frac{1}{2\gamma_k} \right) \|x_{k+1} - x_k\|^2 + \frac{C_2}{2} \|\lambda_k - \lambda^*\| \|x_{k+1} - x_k\|^2 - \langle r_k, x_k - x^* \rangle \\ & \quad + \langle r_{k+1}, x_{k+1} - x^* \rangle + L_{F,\theta} \|\theta_{k+1} - \theta^*\| \|x_{k+1} - x^*\| + L_{x\theta}^\Phi \|\theta_k - \theta^*\| \left(\|x_{k+1} - x_k\| + \|x_k - x^*\| \right) \\ & \quad + \frac{L_{F,x}}{2} \left(\|x_k - x_{k-1}\|^2 - \|x_{k+1} - x_k\|^2 \right) + \frac{L_{F,\theta}}{2} \left(\|\theta_k - \theta_{k-1}\|^2 - \|\theta_{k+1} - \theta_k\|^2 \right) \\ & \quad + L_{\lambda\theta}^\Phi \|\lambda_{k+1} - \lambda^*\| \|\theta_k - \theta^*\| + \frac{J\rho_k}{2} L_{f,\theta}^2 \|\theta_k - \theta^*\|^2 + 2L_{f,\theta} (J\rho_k D_f + \sqrt{J} \|\lambda_k\|) \|\theta_k - \theta^*\|. \end{aligned} \tag{30}$$

To bound the cross term $L_{\lambda\theta}^\Phi \|\lambda_{k+1} - \lambda^*\| \|\theta_k - \theta^*\|$, we apply Young's inequality for any $\alpha_k > 0$

$$L_{\lambda\theta}^\Phi \|\lambda_{k+1} - \lambda^*\| \|\theta_k - \theta^*\| \leq \frac{\alpha_k L_{\lambda\theta}^\Phi}{2} \|\lambda_{k+1} - \lambda^*\|^2 + \frac{L_{\lambda\theta}^\Phi}{2\alpha_k} \|\theta_k - \theta^*\|^2.$$

Using the above inequality in (30), multiplying both sides by $2\rho_k$ and rearranging the terms, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} (1 - \rho_k L_{\lambda\theta}^\Phi \alpha_k) \|\lambda_{k+1} - \lambda^*\|^2 &\leq \|\lambda_k - \lambda^*\|^2 + \rho_k \left(\rho_k C_1 + \|\lambda^*\| C_2 + 2L_{F,x} + L_{F,\theta} - \frac{1}{\gamma_k} \right) \|x_{k+1} - x_k\|^2 \\ &\quad + \rho_k C_2 \|\lambda_k - \lambda^*\| \|x_{k+1} - x_k\|^2 + 2\rho_k (T_k + R_k), \end{aligned} \quad (31)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} T_k &\triangleq \frac{1}{2\gamma_k} \left(\|x_k - x^*\|^2 - \|x_{k+1} - x^*\|^2 \right) + \frac{L_{F,x}}{2} \left(\|x_k - x_{k-1}\|^2 - \|x_{k+1} - x_k\|^2 \right) + \langle r_{k+1}, x_{k+1} - x^* \rangle - \langle r_k, x_k - x^* \rangle, \\ R_k &\triangleq L_{F,\theta} \|\theta_{k+1} - \theta^*\| \|x_{k+1} - x^*\| + L_{x\theta}^\Phi \|\theta_k - \theta^*\| (\|x_{k+1} - x_k\| + \|x_k - x^*\|) + \frac{L_{F,\theta}}{2} \|\theta_k - \theta_{k-1}\|^2 \\ &\quad + \frac{L_{\lambda\theta}^\Phi}{2\alpha_k} \|\theta_k - \theta^*\|^2 + \frac{J\rho_k}{2} L_{f,\theta}^2 \|\theta_k - \theta^*\|^2 + 2L_{f,\theta} (J\rho_k D_f + \sqrt{J} \|\lambda_k\|) \|\theta_k - \theta^*\|. \end{aligned}$$

Assume now that $0 < \rho_k L_{\lambda\theta}^\Phi \alpha_k < 1$. Then, dividing both sides of (31) by $(1 - \rho_k L_{\lambda\theta}^\Phi \alpha_k)$ we get

$$\begin{aligned} \|\lambda_{k+1} - \lambda^*\|^2 &\leq \frac{1}{(1 - \rho_k L_{\lambda\theta}^\Phi \alpha_k)} \|\lambda_k - \lambda^*\|^2 + \frac{\rho_k}{(1 - \rho_k L_{\lambda\theta}^\Phi \alpha_k)} C_2 \|\lambda_k - \lambda^*\| \|x_{k+1} - x_k\|^2 \\ &\quad + \frac{\rho_k}{(1 - \rho_k L_{\lambda\theta}^\Phi \alpha_k)} \left(\rho_k C_1 + \|\lambda^*\| C_2 + 2L_{F,x} + L_{F,\theta} - \frac{1}{\gamma_k} \right) \|x_{k+1} - x_k\|^2 \\ &\quad + \frac{2\rho_k}{(1 - \rho_k L_{\lambda\theta}^\Phi \alpha_k)} (T_k + R_k). \end{aligned} \quad (32)$$

We now provide upper bounds the auxiliary terms T_k and R_k . For T_k summing from $k = 0, \dots, K-1$, using $x_{-1} = x_0$ and $r_0 = 0$, and $\gamma_k = \gamma$ we get

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=0}^{K-1} T_k &= \frac{1}{2\gamma} \left(\|x_0 - x^*\|^2 - \|x_K - x^*\|^2 \right) + \frac{L_{F,x}}{2} \left(\|x_0 - x_{-1}\|^2 - \|x_K - x_{K-1}\|^2 \right) \\ &\quad + \sum_{k=0}^{K-1} \left(\langle r_{k+1}, x_{k+1} - x^* \rangle - \langle r_k, x_k - x^* \rangle \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{2\gamma} \left(\|x_0 - x^*\|^2 - \|x_K - x^*\|^2 \right) + \frac{L_{F,x}}{2} \left(\|x_0 - x_{-1}\|^2 - \|x_K - x_{K-1}\|^2 \right) + \langle r_K, x_K - x^* \rangle. \end{aligned} \quad (33)$$

By Lipschitzness of F in (x, θ) and recalling that $r_K = F(x_K, \theta_K) - F(x_{K-1}, \theta_{K-1})$, one can easily show that $\|r_K\| \leq L_{F,x} \|x_K - x_{K-1}\| + L_{F,\theta} \|\theta_K - \theta_{K-1}\|$. Hence, by Cauchy-Schwarz and Young's inequality

$$\begin{aligned} \langle r_K, x_K - x^* \rangle &\leq (L_{F,x} \|x_K - x_{K-1}\| + L_{F,\theta} \|\theta_K - \theta_{K-1}\|) \|x_K - x^*\| \\ &\leq \frac{L_{F,x}}{2} \|x_K - x_{K-1}\|^2 + \frac{L_{F,x}}{2} \|x_K - x^*\|^2 + \frac{L_{F,\theta}}{2} \|\theta_K - \theta_{K-1}\|^2 + \frac{L_{F,\theta}}{2} \|x_K - x^*\|^2 \\ &= \frac{L_{F,x}}{2} \|x_K - x_{K-1}\|^2 + \frac{L_{F,\theta}}{2} \|\theta_K - \theta_{K-1}\|^2 + \frac{L_{F,x} + L_{F,\theta}}{2} \|x_K - x^*\|^2. \end{aligned}$$

From the definition of T_k and telescoping with $x_{-1} = x_0$ and $r_0 = 0$ in (33), we have

$$\sum_{k=0}^{K-1} T_k \leq \frac{1}{2\gamma} \|x_0 - x^*\|^2 + \left(\frac{L_{F,x} + L_{F,\theta}}{2} - \frac{1}{2\gamma} \right) \|x_K - x^*\|^2 + \frac{L_{F,\theta}}{2} \|\theta_K - \theta_{K-1}\|^2. \quad (34)$$

Choosing $\gamma \in \left(0, (L_{F,x} + L_{F,\theta})^{-1}\right)$ the coefficient of $\|x_K - x^*\|^2$ on the right-hand side of (34) is non-positive and may be discarded. Hence, $\sum_{k=0}^{K-1} T_k \leq \frac{1}{2\gamma} \|x_0 - x^*\|^2 + \frac{L_{F,\theta}}{2} \|\theta_K - \theta_{K-1}\|^2$. By the compactness of Θ , $\|\theta_K - \theta_{K-1}\| \leq \|\theta_K - \theta^*\| + \|\theta_{K-1} - \theta^*\| \leq 2D_\Theta$, it follows that

$$\sum_{k=0}^{K-1} T_k \leq \frac{1}{2\gamma} \|x_0 - x^*\|^2 + 2L_{F,\theta} D_\Theta^2 =: C_T,$$

where $C_T < \infty$ is independent of K . Therefore, for every $K \geq 1$, $\sum_{k=0}^{K-1} T_k \leq C_T$.

Next, we estimate R_k . Again, by the compactness of X , $\|x_{k+1} - x^*\| \leq D_x$ and $\|x_{k+1} - x_k\| \leq \|x_{k+1} - x^*\| + \|x_k - x^*\| \leq 2D_x$. Therefore, for every $k \geq 0$,

$$\begin{aligned} R_k &\leq L_{F,\theta} D_X \|\theta_{k+1} - \theta^*\| + L_{x\theta}^\Phi \|\theta_k - \theta^*\| (2D_X + D_X) + \frac{L_{F,\theta}}{2} \|\theta_k - \theta_{k-1}\|^2 \\ &\quad + \frac{L_{\lambda\theta}^\Phi}{2\alpha_k} \|\theta_k - \theta^*\|^2 + \frac{J\rho_k}{2} L_{f,\theta}^2 \|\theta_k - \theta^*\|^2 + 2L_{f,\theta} (J\rho_k D_f + \sqrt{J} \|\lambda_k\|) \|\theta_k - \theta^*\| \\ &\leq L_{F,\theta} D_X \|\theta_{k+1} - \theta^*\| + \left(3L_{x\theta}^\Phi D_X + 2J\rho_k D_f L_{f,\theta}\right) \|\theta_k - \theta^*\| + \frac{L_{F,\theta}}{2} \|\theta_k - \theta_{k-1}\|^2 \\ &\quad + \left(\frac{L_{\lambda\theta}^\Phi}{2\alpha_k} + \frac{J\rho_k}{2} L_{f,\theta}^2\right) \|\theta_k - \theta^*\|^2 + 2\sqrt{J} L_{f,\theta} \|\lambda_k\| \|\theta_k - \theta^*\|. \end{aligned} \quad (35)$$

Using $\|\theta_k - \theta_{k-1}\|^2 \leq 2\|\theta_k - \theta^*\|^2 + 2\|\theta_{k-1} - \theta^*\|^2$, we further obtain

$$\begin{aligned} R_k &\leq L_{F,\theta} D_X \|\theta_{k+1} - \theta^*\| + \left(3L_{x\theta}^\Phi D_X + 2J\rho_k D_f L_{f,\theta}\right) \|\theta_k - \theta^*\| \\ &\quad + L_{F,\theta} (\|\theta_k - \theta^*\|^2 + \|\theta_{k-1} - \theta^*\|^2) + \left(\frac{L_{\lambda\theta}^\Phi}{2\alpha_k} + \frac{J\rho_k}{2} L_{f,\theta}^2\right) \|\theta_k - \theta^*\|^2 \\ &\quad + 2\sqrt{J} L_{f,\theta} \|\lambda_k\| \|\theta_k - \theta^*\|. \end{aligned} \quad (36)$$

From the induction hypothesis, we have that $\|\lambda_k - \lambda^*\| \leq D_\Lambda$, $k = 0, 1, \dots, K-1$, hence, by the triangle inequality, $\|\lambda_k\| \leq \|\lambda_k - \lambda^*\| + \|\lambda^*\| \leq D_\Lambda + \|\lambda^*\|$, $k = 0, 1, \dots, K-1$. Therefore, for $k = 0, 1, \dots, K-1$, (36) implies

$$\begin{aligned} R_k &\leq L_{F,\theta} D_X \|\theta_{k+1} - \theta^*\| + \left(3L_{x\theta}^\Phi D_X + 2J\rho D_f L_{f,\theta} + 2\sqrt{J} L_{f,\theta} (D_\Lambda + \|\lambda^*\|)\right) \|\theta_k - \theta^*\| \\ &\quad + L_{F,\theta} (\|\theta_k - \theta^*\|^2 + \|\theta_{k-1} - \theta^*\|^2) + \left(\frac{L_{\lambda\theta}^\Phi}{2\alpha_k} + \frac{J\rho}{2} L_{f,\theta}^2\right) \|\theta_k - \theta^*\|^2. \end{aligned} \quad (37)$$

Summing from $k = 0$ to $(K-1)$ and noting that $\theta_{-1} = \theta_0$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=0}^{K-1} R_k &\leq L_{F,\theta} D_X \sum_{k=1}^K \|\theta_k - \theta^*\| + \left(3L_{x\theta}^\Phi D_X + 2J\rho D_f L_{f,\theta} + 2\sqrt{J} L_{f,\theta} (D_\Lambda + \|\lambda^*\|)\right) \sum_{k=0}^{K-1} \|\theta_k - \theta^*\| \\ &\quad + L_{F,\theta} \left(\|\theta_0 - \theta^*\|^2 + 2 \sum_{k=0}^{K-1} \|\theta_k - \theta^*\|^2\right) + \sum_{k=0}^{K-1} \left(\frac{L_{\lambda\theta}^\Phi}{2\alpha_k} + \frac{J\rho}{2} L_{f,\theta}^2\right) \|\theta_k - \theta^*\|^2 =: C_R(D_\Lambda). \end{aligned}$$

Since $\alpha_k = \frac{1}{(k+2)^2} \in (0, 1)$, by the learning-error summability assumption, the right-hand side is finite for each K , and thus $\sum_{k=0}^{K-1} R_k \leq C_R(D_\Lambda)$.

Now define $\delta_k = \frac{1}{1 - \rho_k L_{\lambda^*}^{\Phi} \alpha_k}$, then (32), becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \|\lambda_{k+1} - \lambda^*\|^2 &\leq \delta_k \|\lambda_k - \lambda^*\|^2 + \delta_k \rho_k C_2 \|\lambda_k - \lambda^*\| \|x_{k+1} - x_k\|^2 \\ &\quad + \delta_k \rho_k \left(\rho_k C_1 + \|\lambda^*\| C_2 + 2L_{F,x} + L_{F,\theta} - \frac{1}{\gamma} \right) \|x_{k+1} - x_k\|^2 + 2\delta_k \rho_k (T_k + R_k). \end{aligned} \quad (38)$$

Next, define the sequence $\{t_k\}_{k \geq 0}$ such that $t_0 = 1$ and $t_{k+1} = \frac{t_k}{\delta_k}$ for $k \geq 0$. Based on the parameter selections $\rho_k = \rho = \frac{1}{L_{\lambda^*}^{\Phi}}$ and $\alpha_k = \frac{1}{(k+2)^2}$, we conclude that $t_k = \frac{t_0(k+2)}{2(k+1)}$ which implies that $t_k \in [\frac{1}{2}, 1]$ for any $k \geq 0$. Multiplying both sides of (38) by t_{k+1} , we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} t_{k+1} \|\lambda_{k+1} - \lambda^*\|^2 &\leq t_k \|\lambda_k - \lambda^*\|^2 + \rho_k t_k C_2 \|\lambda_k - \lambda^*\| \|x_{k+1} - x_k\|^2 \\ &\quad + \rho_k t_k \left(\rho_k C_1 + \|\lambda^*\| C_2 + 2L_{F,x} + L_{F,\theta} - \frac{1}{\gamma} \right) \|x_{k+1} - x_k\|^2 + 2\rho_k t_k (T_k + R_k). \end{aligned} \quad (39)$$

We prove the boundedness of the dual iterates by induction, showing that there exists $D_{\Lambda} > 0$ such that $\|\lambda_k - \lambda^*\| \leq D_{\Lambda}$ for all $k \geq 0$. Assume, as the induction hypothesis, that $\|\lambda_k - \lambda^*\| \leq D_{\Lambda}$ for all $k = 0, 1, \dots, K-1$. Hence, we get from (39)

$$\begin{aligned} t_{k+1} \|\lambda_{k+1} - \lambda^*\|^2 &\leq t_k \|\lambda_k - \lambda^*\|^2 + \rho_k t_k \left(\rho_k C_1 + \|\lambda^*\| C_2 + 2L_{F,x} + L_{F,\theta} + C_2 D_{\Lambda} - \frac{1}{\gamma} \right) \|x_{k+1} - x_k\|^2 \\ &\quad + 2\rho_k t_k (T_k + R_k). \end{aligned} \quad (40)$$

Now, for any $\rho_k \equiv \rho > 0$, let us choose γ such that $\gamma \leq (\rho C_1 + \|\lambda^*\| C_2 + 2L_{F,x} + L_{F,\theta} + C_2 D_{\Lambda})^{-1}$, then the coefficient of $\|x_{k+1} - x_k\|^2$ in (40) is non-positive and may be discarded. Therefore, we have

$$t_{k+1} \|\lambda_{k+1} - \lambda^*\|^2 \leq t_k \|\lambda_k - \lambda^*\|^2 + 2\rho t_k (T_k + R_k).$$

Summing this inequality from $k = 0$ to $K-1$ yields

$$t_K \|\lambda_K - \lambda^*\|^2 \leq t_0 \|\lambda_0 - \lambda^*\|^2 + 2\rho \sum_{k=0}^{K-1} t_k (T_k + R_k).$$

Since $t_k \in [\frac{1}{2}, 1]$ for all $k \geq 0$, it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2} \|\lambda_K - \lambda^*\|^2 &\leq \|\lambda_0 - \lambda^*\|^2 + 2\rho \sum_{k=0}^{K-1} (T_k + R_k) \\ &\leq \|\lambda_0 - \lambda^*\|^2 + 2\rho (C_T + C_R(D_{\Lambda})), \end{aligned}$$

where the last inequality follows from the fact that $\sum_{k=0}^{K-1} T_k \leq C_T$ and $\sum_{k=0}^{K-1} R_k \leq C_R(D_{\Lambda})$. Thus, we have

$$\|\lambda_K - \lambda^*\|^2 \leq 2\|\lambda_0 - \lambda^*\|^2 + 4\rho (C_T + C_R(D_{\Lambda})) = 2\|\lambda_0 - \lambda^*\|^2 + \frac{2\rho}{\gamma} \|x_0 - x^*\|^2 + 8\rho L_{F,\theta} D_{\Theta}^2 + 4\rho C_R(D_{\Lambda}),$$

where in the last equality we used the definition of C_T . Since both $\gamma = \mathcal{O}(D_{\Lambda})$ and $C_R(D_{\Lambda}) = \mathcal{O}(D_{\Lambda})$, selecting $D_{\Lambda} \triangleq B + \sqrt{A}$, where $A \triangleq 2\|\lambda_0 - \lambda^*\|^2 + 2\rho \|x_0 - x^*\|^2 (\rho C_1 + \|\lambda^*\| C_2 + 2L_{F,x} + L_{F,\theta}) + 8\rho L_{F,\theta} D_{\Theta}^2 + 4\rho \left(L_{F,\theta} D_X + \right.$

$3L_{x\theta}^\Phi D_X + 2J\rho D_f L_{f,\theta} + 2\sqrt{J}L_{f,\theta}\|\lambda^*\|) \sum_{k=0}^\infty \|\theta_k - \theta^*\| + L_{F,\theta} \left(D_\Theta^2 + 2 \sum_{k=0}^\infty \|\theta_k - \theta^*\|^2 \right) + \frac{L_{\lambda\theta}^\Phi}{2} \sum_{k=0}^\infty \frac{\|\theta_k - \theta^*\|^2}{\alpha_k} + \frac{J\rho}{2} L_{f,\theta}^2 \sum_{k=0}^\infty \|\theta_k - \theta^*\|^2 \Big)$ and $B \triangleq 2\rho C_2 \|x_0 - x^*\|^2 + 8\rho\sqrt{J} L_{f,\theta} \sum_{k=0}^\infty \|\theta_k - \theta^*\|$, implies that $\|\lambda_K - \lambda^*\|^2 \leq D_\Lambda^2$ which completes the induction, hence, the result is proved. \square

E. Proof of Theorem 1

Proof From (29), for every $k \geq 0, x \in X, \lambda \in \mathbb{R}_+^J$, we have

$$(x_{k+1} - x)^\top F(x, \theta^*) + \sum_{j=1}^J \lambda^{(j)} f_j(x_{k+1}, \theta^*) - \Phi_\rho(x, \lambda_k, \theta^*) \leq \mathcal{T}_k(x) + \mathcal{R}_k(x, \lambda) + \frac{1}{2\rho} (\|\lambda_k - \lambda\|^2 - \|\lambda_{k+1} - \lambda\|^2), \quad (41)$$

where we grouped terms as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{T}_k(x) &\triangleq \frac{1}{2\gamma} (\|x_k - x\|^2 - \|x_{k+1} - x\|^2) + \frac{L_{F,x}}{2} (\|x_k - x_{k-1}\|^2 - \|x_{k+1} - x_k\|^2) \\ &\quad + \langle r_{k+1}, x_{k+1} - x \rangle - \langle r_k, x_k - x \rangle, \\ \mathcal{R}_k(x, \lambda) &\triangleq \left(\frac{\rho_k C_1 + \|\lambda^*\| C_2 + 2L_{F,x} + L_{F,\theta}}{2} - \frac{1}{2\gamma_k} \right) \|x_{k+1} - x_k\|^2 + \frac{C_2}{2} \|\lambda_k - \lambda^*\| \|x_{k+1} - x_k\|^2 \\ &\quad + \frac{L_{F,\theta}}{2} \|\theta_{k+1} - \theta_k\|^2 + \frac{L_{F,\theta}}{2} (\|\theta_k - \theta_{k-1}\|^2 - \|\theta_{k+1} - \theta_k\|^2) + L_{F,\theta} \|\theta_{k+1} - \theta^*\| \|x_{k+1} - x\| \\ &\quad + L_{x\theta}^\Phi \|\theta_k - \theta^*\| (\|x_{k+1} - x_k\| + \|x_k - x\|) + L_{\lambda\theta}^\Phi \|\lambda_{k+1} - \lambda\| \|\theta_k - \theta^*\| \\ &\quad + \frac{J\rho}{2} L_{f,\theta}^2 \|\theta_k - \theta^*\|^2 + 2L_{f,\theta} (J\rho D_f + \sqrt{J} \|\lambda_k\|) \|\theta_k - \theta^*\|. \end{aligned}$$

Moving $-\Phi_\rho(x, \lambda_k, \theta^*)$ to the right in (41), then summing over $k = 0, \dots, K-1$ and dividing by K , and using convexity of each $f_j(\cdot, \theta^*)$ to pass the average inside, we get

$$\begin{aligned} (\bar{x}_K - x)^\top F(x, \theta^*) + f(\bar{x}_K, \theta^*)^\top \lambda &\leq \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=0}^{K-1} \Phi_\rho(x, \lambda_k, \theta^*) + \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=0}^{K-1} (\mathcal{T}_k(x) + \mathcal{R}_k(x, \lambda)) \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2\rho} (\|\lambda_0 - \lambda\|^2 - \|\lambda_K - \lambda\|^2). \end{aligned} \quad (42)$$

Considering $\sum_{k=0}^{K-1} \mathcal{T}_k(x)$, telescoping in the x -terms and the r_k -pair, we have

$$\sum_{k=0}^{K-1} \mathcal{T}_k(x) = \frac{1}{2\gamma} (\|x_0 - x\|^2 - \|x_K - x\|^2) - \frac{L_{F,x}}{2} \|x_K - x_{K-1}\|^2 + \langle r_K, x_K - x \rangle.$$

Note that $\|r_K\| \leq L_{F,x} \|x_K - x_{K-1}\| + L_{F,\theta} \|\theta_K - \theta_{K-1}\|$, therefore $\langle r_K, x_K - x \rangle \leq \frac{L_{F,x}}{2} \|x_K - x_{K-1}\|^2 + \frac{L_{F,x}}{2} \|x_K - x\|^2 + L_{F,\theta} \|\theta_K - \theta_{K-1}\| \|x_K - x\|$. Substituting this into the previous equality, we have

$$\sum_{k=0}^{K-1} \mathcal{T}_k(x) = \frac{1}{2\gamma} \|x_0 - x\|^2 + \left(\frac{L_{F,x}}{2} - \frac{1}{2\gamma} \right) \|x_K - x\|^2 + L_{F,\theta} \|\theta_K - \theta_{K-1}\| \|x_K - x\|.$$

Choosing $\gamma \in (0, L_{F,x}^{-1})$, the coefficient of $\|x_K - x\|^2$ is non-positive and can be discarded. Since $x, x_0, x_K \in X$ and $\theta_K, \theta_{K-1} \in \Theta$, we have $\|x_0 - x\| \leq D_X$, $\|x_K - x\| \leq D_X$, and $\|\theta_K - \theta_{K-1}\| \leq 2D_\Theta$. Therefore,

$$\sum_{k=0}^{K-1} \mathcal{T}_k(x) \leq \frac{1}{2\gamma} D_X^2 + 2L_{F,\theta} D_X D_\Theta \triangleq C'_T \quad \forall K, \quad \forall x \in X. \quad (43)$$

Next, we focus on $\sum_{k=0}^{K-1} \mathcal{R}_k(x, \lambda)$. By continuity on the compact sets X, Θ we have that $\sup_{x \in X, \theta \in \Theta} |f_j(x, \theta^*)| \leq D_f$ for all $j = 1, \dots, J$. Now, let the constant-parameters $\rho_k \equiv \rho > 0$ and $\gamma_k \equiv \gamma > 0$. By Lemma 5, the dual sequence is bounded, and hence there exists $D_\Lambda > 0$ such that $\|\lambda_k - \lambda^*\| \leq D_\Lambda$ for all $k \geq 0$. Therefore, $\frac{C_2}{2} \|\lambda_k - \lambda^*\| \|x_{k+1} - x_k\|^2 \leq \frac{C_2 D_\Lambda}{2} \|x_{k+1} - x_k\|^2$. Consequently, if the primal step-size is chosen so that $\gamma \in \left(0, (\rho C_1 + \|\lambda^*\| C_2 + 2L_{F,x} + L_{F,\theta} + C_2 D_\Lambda)^{-1}\right)$, then the whole coefficient of $\|x_{k+1} - x_k\|^2$ in $\mathcal{R}_k(x, \lambda)$ is non-positive and may be discarded. The remaining terms in $\mathcal{R}_k(x, \lambda)$ are controlled by the boundedness of X, Θ , and $\{\lambda_k\}_{k \geq 0}$ together with the learning-error summability assumption. In particular, since $\|\lambda_k\| \leq \|\lambda_k - \lambda^*\| + \|\lambda^*\| \leq D_\Lambda + \|\lambda^*\|$, the last term $2L_{f,\theta}(J\rho D_f + \sqrt{J}\|\lambda_k\|)\|\theta_k - \theta^*\|$ is bounded by $2L_{f,\theta}(J\rho D_f + \sqrt{J}(D_\Lambda + \|\lambda^*\|))\|\theta_k - \theta^*\|$ which together with $\frac{J\rho}{2} L_{f,\theta}^2 \|\theta_k - \theta^*\|^2$ are summable by the learning-error assumption. Therefore, we conclude that $\sum_{k=0}^{K-1} \mathcal{R}_k(x, \lambda) \leq C'_R(x, \lambda)$ where

$$\begin{aligned} C'_R(x, \lambda) \triangleq & \left(L_{F,\theta} D_X + 2L_{x\theta}^\Phi D_X + 2L_{\lambda\theta}^\Phi D_\Lambda + 2L_{f,\theta}(J\rho D_f + \sqrt{J}(D_\Lambda + \|\lambda^*\|)) \right) \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \|\theta_k - \theta^*\| \\ & + \left(L_{F,\theta} + \frac{J\rho}{2} L_{f,\theta}^2 \right) \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \|\theta_k - \theta^*\|^2 < +\infty. \end{aligned} \quad (44)$$

Using (43) and (44) in (42), we get

$$\begin{aligned} & (\bar{x}_K - x)^\top F(x, \theta^*) + f(\bar{x}_K, \theta^*)^\top \lambda \\ & \leq \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=0}^{K-1} \Phi_\rho(x, \lambda_k, \theta^*) + \frac{C'_T + C'_R(x, \lambda)}{K} + \frac{1}{2\rho K} (\|\lambda_0 - \lambda\|^2 - \|\lambda_K - \lambda\|^2). \end{aligned} \quad (45)$$

Let $x = x^*$ within (45). Since $x^* \in \mathcal{X}(\theta^*)$, we have $\Phi_\rho(x^*, \lambda_k, \theta^*) \leq 0$ for all k , hence

$$(\bar{x}_K - x^*)^\top F(x^*, \theta^*) + f(\bar{x}_K, \theta^*)^\top \lambda \leq \frac{C'_T + C'_R(x^*, \lambda)}{K} + \frac{1}{2\rho K} (\|\lambda_0 - \lambda\|^2 - \|\lambda_K - \lambda\|^2). \quad (46)$$

By Lemma 1, evaluated at (x^*, λ^*) , we have

$$(\bar{x}_K - x^*)^\top F(x^*, \theta^*) + [f(\bar{x}_K, \theta^*)]_+^\top \lambda^* \geq 0. \quad (47)$$

Subtracting (47) from (46) eliminates $(\bar{x}_K - x^*)^\top F(x^*, \theta^*)$ and yields

$$\left(f(\bar{x}_K, \theta^*)^\top \lambda - [f(\bar{x}_K, \theta^*)]_+^\top \lambda^* \right) \leq \frac{C'_T + C'_R(x^*, \lambda)}{K} + \frac{1}{2\rho K} (\|\lambda_0 - \lambda\|^2 - \|\lambda_K - \lambda\|^2), \quad \forall \lambda \in \mathbb{R}_+^J. \quad (48)$$

Let $\lambda = \tilde{\lambda}$ within (48) such that $\tilde{\lambda}_j \triangleq \begin{cases} 1 + \lambda_j^*, & \text{if } f_j(\bar{x}_K, \theta^*) > 0 \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$, hence, $f(\bar{x}_K, \theta^*)^\top \tilde{\lambda} - [f(\bar{x}_K, \theta^*)]_+^\top \lambda^* = \mathbf{1}^\top [f(\bar{x}_K, \theta^*)]_+$ which implies that

$$\mathbf{1}^\top [f(\bar{x}_K, \theta^*)]_+ \leq \frac{C'_T + C'_R(x^*, \tilde{\lambda})}{K} + \frac{J + \|\lambda_0 - \lambda^*\|^2}{\rho K} = \frac{C_{\text{feas}}}{K}, \quad (49)$$

where $C_{\text{feas}} = C'_T + \left(L_{F,\theta} D_X + 2L_{x\theta}^\Phi D_X + 2L_{\lambda\theta}^\Phi D_\Lambda + 2L_{f,\theta}(J\rho D_f + \sqrt{J}(D_\Lambda + \|\lambda^*\|)) \right) \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \|\theta_k - \theta^*\| + \left(L_{F,\theta} + \frac{J\rho}{2} L_{f,\theta}^2 \right) \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \|\theta_k - \theta^*\|^2 + \frac{J + \|\lambda_0 - \lambda^*\|^2}{\rho}$.

Moreover, if we define $\epsilon \triangleq \frac{C_{\text{feas}}}{K}$ and the enlarged feasible set $\mathcal{X}_\epsilon(\theta^*) = \{x \in X \mid \mathbf{1}^\top [f(x, \theta^*)]_+ \leq \epsilon\}$. Then, $\sum_{j=1}^J [f_j(x, \theta^*)]_+ \leq \epsilon$, and using the definition of Φ_ρ together with $\|\lambda_k\| \leq D_\Lambda$ yields

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi_\rho(x, \lambda_k, \theta^*) &= \sum_{j=1}^J \frac{([\lambda_k^{(j)} + \rho f_j(x, \theta^*)]_+)^2 - (\lambda_k^{(j)})^2}{2\rho} \\ &\leq \sum_{j=1}^J \left(\lambda_k^{(j)} [f_j(x, \theta^*)]_+ + \frac{\rho}{2} [f_j(x, \theta^*)]_+^2 \right) \\ &\leq D_\Lambda \mathbf{1}^\top [f(x, \theta^*)]_+ + \frac{\rho}{2} (\mathbf{1}^\top [f(x, \theta^*)]_+)^2 \\ &\leq D_\Lambda \epsilon + \frac{\rho}{2} \epsilon^2. \end{aligned}$$

Note that this bound is uniform in k . Therefore, we have $\frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=0}^{K-1} \Phi_\rho(x, \lambda_k, \theta^*) \leq D_\Lambda \epsilon + \frac{\rho}{2} \epsilon^2$. Now, let $\lambda = \mathbf{0}$ in (45) to conclude that

$$\begin{aligned} (\bar{x}_K - x)^\top F(x, \theta^*) &\leq \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=0}^{K-1} \Phi_\rho(x, \lambda_k, \theta^*) + \frac{C'_T + C'_R(x, 0)}{K} \\ &\leq D_\Lambda \epsilon + \frac{\rho}{2} \epsilon^2 + \frac{C'_T + C'_R(x, 0)}{K} \\ &\leq D_\Lambda \frac{C_{\text{feas}}}{K} + \frac{\rho}{2} \left(\frac{C_{\text{feas}}}{K} \right)^2 + \frac{C'_T + C'_R(x, 0)}{K}. \end{aligned} \quad (50)$$

Taking the supremum over $x \in \mathcal{X}_{\epsilon_K}(\theta^*)$ gives

$$\widetilde{\text{Gap}}(\bar{x}_K, \theta^*) \triangleq \sup_{x \in \mathcal{X}_{\epsilon_K}(\theta^*)} F(x, \theta^*)^\top (\bar{x}_K - x) \leq \frac{C'_T + C'_R(x, 0)}{K} + D_\Lambda \frac{C_{\text{feas}}}{K} + \frac{\rho}{2} \left(\frac{C_{\text{feas}}}{K} \right)^2, \quad (51)$$

where C'_T , and C_{feas} are defined as above and $C'_R(x, 0) = \left(L_{F, \theta} D_X + 2L_{x\theta}^\Phi D_X + 2L_{\lambda\theta}^\Phi D_\Lambda + 2L_{f, \theta} (J_\rho D_f + \sqrt{J} (D_\Lambda + \|\lambda^*\|)) \right) \sum_{k=0}^\infty \|\theta_k - \theta^*\| + \left(L_{F, \theta} + \frac{J\rho}{2} L_{f, \theta}^2 \right) \sum_{k=0}^\infty \|\theta_k - \theta^*\|^2$. \square